

EELISA

European University

**EELISA INNOCORE - EELISA MULTI LABS (SHARING
FACILITIES & EQUIPMENT)**

Deliverable D4.1 - Mapping of existing facilities

Date: 30/09/2022

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

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Executive summary

The first aim of WP4 is to promote a fluid use and access of the existing research facilities for the EELISA community. To this end, the first task is focused on the identification and listing of the existing resources within EELISA. The facilities we will target are not only those already part of international network, but also technological platforms or resources developed by EELISA partners willing to open them either in a collaborative or partnership fashion. This mapping will also allow to identify a network of facilities available for teaching purposes (ex. allowing the setup of teaching modules across the different platforms of the partners) both for a researcher and student public.

This work will provide a mapping (D4.1) that will be shared on the EELISA website and will contribute to the attractiveness of the Alliance. Increasing the visibility of the infrastructures will help in connecting researchers and in spreading the use of the specific procedures and methods developed by the EELISA partners, thus significantly contributing in enhancing their visibility. Furthermore, this network will allow the creation of a unique environment for teaching allowing students to access not only well-established instrumental setups but also state of the art research infrastructures and techniques in a large variety of fields.

To collect information needed for the mapping, a common survey was designed and distributed by the each EELISA partner among its academic staff and platform/technical managers to gather the information. To further motivate the feeding of the survey, it was presented in dissemination activities organized within EELISA. Finally, the group checked the quality of the data and suggested further actions to improve the catalogue and its usability for researchers.

The actual document of mapping is currently under revision and will be realised on the EELISA website in a few weeks following the publication of the present document.

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Responsibles for WP4

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Review and quality check by EELISA

To guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between different Innocore and EELISA actions, the following people from EELISA have been consulted for the production of this deliverable: Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa and Isabel Salgueiro from UPM and Emrah Acar and Bersam Bolat from ITU.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

ESFRI: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. It is composed of national delegates nominated by research ministers of EU countries and countries associated with Horizon 2020. It also includes a Commission representative. ESFRI is a self-regulated body, operating on a consensus basis. The main activity of the Forum is to establish a European roadmap for Research Infrastructures for the next 10-20 years, stimulate the implementation of these facilities.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

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Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centres, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

Strategic Research Areas. The research areas selected as “strategic” by the EELISA consortium at the Kick-off meeting in September 2021. There are 11 areas:

- Artificial intelligence
- Connectivity
- Social sciences and humanities
- Digitalization
- Health
- Smart industry and space technologies
- Advanced material science and engineering
- Culture, creativity and inclusive society
- Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment
- Climate, energy and mobility
- Natural Sciences

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 43 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the research and innovation (R&I) dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks); and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE is running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industrial stakeholders (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 Rationale – “Creating Multi Labs”

Currently, at European level, developments related to research infrastructures are mostly related to (very) large facilities (e.g., via ESFRI) that lead to a series of projects bringing outstanding outcomes to the European Union and international community.

At the European University level, EELISA has identified a complementary need linked to this work: sharing research infrastructures and other resources available *at local level* which has been called “Create Multi Labs”. Indeed, the creation of EELISA Multi Labs, will be an unprecedented experience of collaboration between our institutions via facilities. The sharing of facilities will empower our researchers, under principles of solidarity and efficiency while making our institutions more resilient at local level before setting up new medium to large size facilities.

The three main objectives of the work group are:

- Promote shared utilization of available infrastructures among partner universities
- Optimize allocation of new local facilities
- Prepare the ground for setting up joint facilities

This will be achieved through the creation of a simple system connecting facilities and equipment to users. EELISA labs will be connected via the sharing of facilities, the set-up of new facilities, or ultimately the creation of joint facilities...

The outcomes of the current and planned work are very diverse:

- Increased mobility projects of staff and students
- Mobility patterns
- Visiting researcher positions (faculty) or short-term scientific missions
- International research experiences (graduate students including MSc and PhD)
- Increased number of workshops and training organised
- PhD with dual advisors
- Increased number of co-authored research papers in peer-reviewed journals
- Increased volume of external funding

Before connecting facilities, it is necessary to make a mapping of them which is the very first task of the work group during the first and a half year of InnoCORE.

3 Methodology

As mentioned in the general summary, the overall target of the deliverable is the mapping (D4.1) that will be shared on the EELISA website of the existing research infrastructures and technological platforms present in the EELISA consortium.

To collect the information needed for the mapping, the members of the WP4 designed a survey to be distributed by each EELISA partner among its academic staff and platform/technical managers to gather the information. The main guidelines that were followed to develop the survey were:

- get essential information about the infrastructure (responsibility, characteristic, load, possibility of access)
- get essential information enabling to link each infrastructure to the strategic research areas defined by EELISA

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- be rapid and easy to be filled for the academic staff
- be easily inter-operational with EELISA partners existing catalogues

Following the consensus on the design of survey (reached during the meeting held on 17 February 2022), it was distributed at the end of February 2022, and then internally disseminated. A first survey of the result was discussed during a WP4 meeting on 7 April 2022 and, as measure to further promote the survey filling it was decided to promote the visibility of the survey during the dissemination activities the EELISA consortium (e.g., onboarding session). In this latter the activities and aims of WP4 were thus presented as well as the survey.

The data obtained were analysed and collected in a first version of the catalogue (compiled as a pdf file) that was discussed with the partners during the meeting on 17 June 2022.

The actual document of mapping is currently under revision and will be realised on the EELISA website in few weeks after the publication of the present document (see Section 5. Next steps).

3.1 Set-up of the Survey

On the basis of the main guidelines listed above, a survey was designed and approved by the WP4 working group. This survey is available in Annex I. The survey will be open for the full project duration to allow a dynamic feeding of the catalogue.

Additionally, data coming from existing databases were also collected and integrated. UPM was the only partner for which a detailed mapping of existing facilities was available² (this work has started two years ago and is still on-going). These data were thus fully integrated into the survey outcome.

For each of the facilities (classed as a function of the host institution and research area) we asked about the type and main aim of the facility and to provide a short description allowing the possibility to provide a link to existing website or on-line documents if available.

The willingness of each institution to open the facilities to the EELISA communities as well as the eventual existing rules of access were also requested to prepare the deliverable.

3.2 Dissemination

The representative of each institution in WP4 decided the most appropriate way of distributing the survey among their research communities. In most cases this was performed by delivering the survey to the research communities by email or via presentations delivered in relevant committees

UPM did not distributed this survey since information was directly retrieved from their existing catalogue. Analogously BME is currently working on their own catalogue which prevented them to distribute and feed the survey.

In addition, an EELISA wide event (On-Boarding session) has been organised on 30 May 2022 to increase the visibility of the work³.

² cf. <https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/>

³ cf. <https://psl.eu/en/events/eelisa-onboarding-session>

4 Discussion

After 6 months, the catalogue includes 220 entries in total. An analysis of the main figures is presented in the following sections.

4.1 Host Institution

The first question of the survey was related to the institution hosting the facility. 7 out of the 9 members of the consortium are represented in the catalogue, except for BME and ENPC. While the number of respondents is not representative of the infrastructures present in each institution (for example only 3 for PSL or 6 for FAU), the results obtained are encouraging. The number of respondents per institution also seems to be strongly dependent on the volume of requests received by the different academic audiences in each institution. ITU seems to have succeeded in their communication to incentivise academics to fill out the survey, as well as SNS or SSSA due to the presence of structured research platforms. However, since 142 out of 220 entries are coming from the existing UPM catalogue, the present results cannot be considered as a realistic and sincere picture of the research infrastructures present in the EELISA consortium. Countermeasures are proposed in Section 5 Next steps.

Figure 1 – Distribution of the infrastructures among the EELISA institutions

4.2 Type and purpose of facilities

The aim of the WP is to provide visibility of different type of facilities (from a single state of the art equipment developed in research laboratories to existing technological platform whether for research or teaching). Therefore, it was interesting to analyse the type and purpose of research facilities in the EELISA consortium.

From the data collected, we can see that the facilities currently listed in the catalogue correspond either to a single or several equipment not necessarily already structured as a platform (51%) or to well-defined platform (40%), while only 9% of the infrastructures are actually corresponding to open teaching laboratories. Of note 75% of the infrastructures identified as platforms (scientific or technological infrastructures in Figure 2) are actually located at UPM.

Figure 2 shows that most of the facilities are devoted to research activities (215 over 220) but a significant number of the is also dedicated to teaching (185 over 220) or open to industrial partners (164 over 220).

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Figure 2 - Type and purpose of facilities

4.3 Strategic research areas

In EELISA InnoCORE, an initial work via WP2 has been achieved to define Strategic Research Areas (SRA) as a common language between members. So, we decided that each facility should be indexed on the basis of the research area and that one facility could belong to more than one strategic research area.

Interestingly all strategic research areas are represented in the survey. The data are, as previously mentioned, biased by the uneven distribution of the collected research facilities among the partners (see point 3.1). Nonetheless, given the profile of EELISA members, it is not surprising that research areas such as “social science and humanities” or “culture creativity and inclusive society” are less represented (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Strategic research areas for the collected research facilities

4.4 Access rules and accessibility

One of the possible issues identified for WP4 was the diversity of conditions under which a facility can be made available. Therefore, two specific questions were included in the survey to get an insight of the state of the art in this respect.

All facilities belonging to the UPM have common established rules of access (142 yes entries in Figure 4), while almost 2/3 of the facilities from other institutions do not have pre-defined access rules (55 no entries in Figure 4).

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Figure 4 - Presence of access rules for the existing facilities (blue yes correspond to the UPM fixed access conditions, see text)

Further analysis of the conditions of access that these facilities (i.e. the non UPM one) would prefer (Figure 5) points out a significant dispersion in the responses, giving us an important input for the discussion about sharing and opening conditions that will be included in the next deliverable of this WP D4.2 Agreement on the main consensual rules of access to open facilities.

Figure 5 - Preferred conditions of access for the facilities (not including UPM ones)

Finally, the actual availability of the facilities was analysed. Indeed, as the Alliance is mostly composed by research-intensive institutions, we expected that some of facilities could be already largely loaded, which would mechanically limit their availability for new collaborations.

Figure 6 shows that the situation is rather mixed: while 42% of the facilities has a very high load, the remaining are relatively available to be used.

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Figure 6 – Current load of facilities

4.5 Quality

The survey results allow to draw a global picture of facilities in EELISA despite the uneven distribution of the answers across partners.

To make survey data usable, it is necessary to show them as an actual catalogue. At this stage, quality of data is key so that we can make user friendly presentation of what exist in EELISA.

Unfortunately, even with an automatic retrieve of data, a systematic effort is to be paid to obtain a concise and clear description of the facility that would encourage other researchers to get in contact with the person responsible for facility and finally lead to new research or teaching project.

Currently, out of the 220 entries of the catalogue, approximately one third are incomplete or inconsistent. The main issues were related to:

- Name of the equipment not self-explaining
- Description missing or not in English
- Photo not available especially when it is related to a set of equipment

Furthermore, while the integration of the existing database led to high-quality data, it does not allow a direct engagement of the responsible of the facilities. Conversely, the survey enabled some partners to engage with their internal scientific community, although the accuracy of data is lower.

This question has been thoroughly discussed during the June meeting and in Madrid on 22 September 2022 leading to a consensus about the fact that increasing the quality of the data will be possible by making the catalogue useful for those who will feed it. Indeed, it is expected that one would pay more attention to the data he/she can give to the catalogue if he/she knows that the positive impact on activities will be greater.

5 Next steps

Following the discussion of the first set of results, the group identified three ways to move forward to maximize impact on researchers within EELISA.

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5.1 Visibility

The current lack of visibility of the catalogue is one of the main reasons of low engagement from researchers. Thanks to UPM experience with its own catalogue, it is expected that when the EELISA website will host the catalogue – even with very limited functionalities – this will boost the number of entries.

Currently on the EELISA website there is a dedicated section on research⁴. In addition, the EELISA communication team has already set up a catalogue of courses. A reasonable level of effort is necessary to adapt it to our needs. Users could search and access to the list per research area and will be allowed to get in contact with the person responsible of the relevant facility. This is a first step toward a more elaborated system that is planned to be implemented during the 2nd part of InnoCORE (cf. Deliverable 4.3 Definition of the main features of the IT booking system).

5.2 Mobility

All partners agreed that specific mobility actions allowing short-term scientific missions of researchers on the facilities would boost the adhesion to the catalogue. Discussions are ongoing to define the best way to implement this type of mobility within the EELISA partners.

For instance, processes for Erasmus mobility for staffs or PhD could be drastically simplified for applicants when they rely on the catalogue to prepare a short stay in a partner institution.

5.3 Dynamics.

Finally, partner institutions agree that a catalogue should be a living platform that requires a continuous enrichment and updating effort. The use of specific tools that ease continuous feeding by partner institutions would convert a vitrine to a live catalogue, with a quality check at each step of the process.

6 Conclusion

The gathering of data from facilities in each EELISA partner follow its own pace and is the consequence of the diversity of the Alliance.

However, the initial results show that there is an apparent willingness to open existing facilities and equipment to foster various types of collaborations. We have identified possible bottleneck to our work:

- 1) The need to bring more visibility to the catalogue and 2) making it a live process.

The first task will be achieved by a publication on the EELISA website while the latter falls within the scope of the next deliverable D4.3 Definition of the main features of the IT booking system.

There is a clear need to identify added values from the researcher point of view to be an active part in the setting up of the catalogue. In this respect, mobility grants linked to research facilities will be explored to facilitate the movement of researchers within EELISA.

⁴ Cf. <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-innocore/>

Annex I – On-line Survey

The survey is available via this link:

<https://framaforms.org/developing-collaborations-within-eelisa-via-access-to-facilities-and-equipment-1646650740>

Rationale

In order to allow and promote **a fluid use of existing research facilities**, we wish to identify the existing resources among EELISA partners. We target **technological platforms or resources developed by EELISA partners willing to open them either in a collaborative or partnership fashion**. This mapping will also identify facilities for teaching purposes both for a researcher and student public.

Currently the degree of openness of facilities is very different among partners and research fields. While some platform facilities are open, rules of access may be significantly different. The objective is twofold 1) give more visibility to facilities 2) facilitate their share via supporting the definition of access rights.

Survey to identify facilities and conditions for sharing them

Hereafter the survey as distributed

By filling this survey, you agree to give visibility to the facility you will describe so that colleagues from EELISA partners might contact you to know more about it and possibly start a new collaboration. Nevertheless, there is no engagement to accept such new collaborations.

1. Description of the facility

What is your EELISA institution?

- Technical University of Madrid (UPM)
- Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)
- Ecoles des Ponts ParisTech (PONTS)
- Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)
- Istanbul Technical University (ITU)
- Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)
- Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA)
- Politehnica University of Bucharest (UPB)
- Université PSL (PSL)

Is the facility

- A single equipment
 - Did you develop / customize it in your laboratory/team?
 - Yes
 - No
- A technological platform
- A FabLab / Open teaching laboratory

If it is single equipment, please provide the name of the laboratory/team where it is:

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If it is a platform or a FabLab, please provide its name:

If your facility is already described on a webpage or a database, please provide the link:

If, no please provide:

A photo:

A brief description:

Is the facility for: (several answers possible)

- Research activities
- Teaching activities
- Other activities (industrial...)

○ If other:

In which EELISA areas would you link your facility? (several answers possible)

- Artificial intelligence
- Connectivity
- Social sciences and humanities
- Digitalization
- Health
- Smart industry and space technologies
- Advanced material science and engineering
- Culture, creativity and inclusive society
- Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment
- Climate, energy and mobility
- Natural Sciences

2. Condition for accessing the facility

Do you already have access rules for this facility?

- Yes
- No

If yes, where can they be found (website or document):

If no, what would be your conditions:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA

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- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague come under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration
- To be agreed in a collaboration agreement
- Other rules

If other, please elaborate your conditions:

3. Making the facility visible to EELISA

Who is the person to contact if a colleague from EELISA would like to have more information?

- First name :
- LAST NAME :
- Position :
- Email :

One of the goals of EELISA is to build a public catalogue of such facilities to give them more visibility and nurture new European collaboration, are you happy that those data can be reused for

- This current mapping exercise (leading to a one-shot deliverable)
- A future one-line catalogue (that can be regularly updated)

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Annex II – Sample of the catalogue

The data collected were firstly collected as an excel spreadsheet that guarantees interoperability with UPM. These data next served to produce a static pdf catalogue. A sampling of both files is here provided.

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INFRA_ID	INFRA_UNIV	INFRA_TYPE	INFRA_DVT	INFRA_RS	INFRA_NAME	INFRA_DESC	WEBSITE_EXI ST	WEBSITE	PHOTO	INFRA_LO AD	SHARE_EXISI TING_RULE	SHARE_LINK	CONTACT_NA ME	CONTACT_LA ST_NAME	CONTACT_PO SITION	CONTACT_RS	AGREE_MAPP NG	AGREE_CATA LOG	INFRA_DOMAINS	INFRA_TEACH RESEAR	SHARE	
11924745	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)	An open teaching laboratory		Department of Materials Sciences and Engineering	Chair of Glass and Ceramics	The following equipment can be available in joint research projects within the EELISA network: Contact: Prof. Dr. Kyle G. Webber anACCT TF 2000 ferroelectric testing system (1-250 °C) Temperature- and atmosphere-dependent ovens (up to 900 °C) for dielectric measurements and impedance spectroscopy Impedance spectrometer (Novocontrol Alpha-A Analyzer) and various LCR meters Screw-type load frames for temperature dependent mechanical and electrical measurements in compression (-150 °C to 450 °C, 30kN) Aerosol deposition system for room temperature of thick films (ceramics, glasses, and metals) Contact: Prof. Dr. Dominique de Ligny Arabic Raman Fluorolog UV-Vis Furnace to melt glass Contact: Prof. Dr. habil. Nahum Travitzky 3D printing equipment (powder bed, robo casting) Contact: PD Dr.-Ing. habil. Tobias Fey µCT Skyscan 1172 (max. resolution 0.7 µm) 3D-FDM printer Prusa mix (PVA, PLA, PETG, ABS, TPU) 3D-stereolithography DLP printer AnyCubic (Photon, Mono, Mono X) 3D-stereolithography DWS 020 printer Injection moulding technology Contact: PD Dr. rer. nat. Stephan E. Wolf 2x Titrande automated titration systems	yes	https://www.glass-ceramics.f.fau.de/eelisa/	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no			Dominique	DE LIGNY		Department of Materials Sciences and Engineering	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility/Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility	Research activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA
11671483	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Academics and graduate students	Architectural Conservation Laboratory- Faculty of Architecture	The laboratory is concentrated on works of characterization of historic building materials, conservation, and consolidation of mortars, plasters, and stone.	no		nophoto.png	Almost fully used	yes		İşıl	POLAT PEKMEZCI		Academics and graduate students	X	X	Culture creativity and inclusive society/Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...)		
13067627	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Sampling/testing/reporting	Architectural Conservation Laboratory/Minari Koruma Laboratuvarı	Architectural Conservation Laboratory is a research and teaching laboratory concentrated on the characterization and conservation of traditional building materials. The laboratory is the venue for several graduate courses in the Master's and Ph.D. programs of Architectural Conservation/Restoration at ITU. The lab provides a research environment for graduate students who are working on these topics.	no		nophoto.png	Almost fully used	no		İşıl	POLAT PEKMEZCI	Associate Prof	Sampling/testing/reporting	X		Social sciences and humanities - Culture creativity and inclusive society/Social sciences and humanities - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...) - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
12910355	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Artificial Intelligence	computers used for the design and implementation of deep learning algorithms	Monitoring modern technologies and technology development in multimodal signal processing and pattern recognition at ITU.	yes	https://www.mis.yr.itu.edu.tr	nophoto.png	Almost fully used	no		Bilge	GÜNSEL	Lab manager	Artificial Intelligence		X	Artificial intelligence/Artificial intelligence	Research activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)	
12943575	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Geotechnical engineering, earthquake engineering, geomechanics	Earthquake Engineering R&D Lab	Our laboratory has a small-scale shaking table with test systems that determine some soil mechanics, physical and engineering properties. Triaxial pressure test device with suction control to measure the stress-strain and strength properties of unsaturated soils and the "hydrop device", which simultaneously determines the water retention and hydraulic conductivity behavior of the soil with the method of drying in open air, have been brought to our university. In addition, the water purification device with a purification	yes	https://eemf.itu.edu.tr/en/research/laboratories/earthquake-engineering-r-d-laboratory	nophoto.png	Lower than 50% used	no		Mehmet	ULKER	Lab director	Geotechnical engineering, earthquake engineering, geomechanics	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering/Advanced material science and engineering	Research, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
12906911	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Research Centre	EMCOL research centre	EMCOL is designed to combine the trained scientists in Istanbul Technical University (ITU) with advanced field and laboratory facilities for marine and lake studies. EMCOL houses, administers and utilises the upgraded facilities and train new researchers in advanced methodologies in marine geology-geophysics, paleoceanography and limnology.	yes	www.emcol.itu.edu.tr	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Kürşad Kadir	ERİŞ	Profesör	Research Centre	X	X	Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences/Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
12906919	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Research Centre	EMCOL research centre	EMCOL is designed to combine the trained scientists in Istanbul Technical University (ITU) with advanced field and laboratory facilities for marine and lake studies. EMCOL houses, administers and utilises the upgraded facilities and train new researchers in advanced methodologies in marine geology-geophysics, paleoceanography and limnology.	yes	www.emcol.itu.edu.tr	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Kürşad Kadir	ERİŞ	academician	Research Centre	X	X	Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences/Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
13047484	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Marine Engineering	Engine Room Simulator	Ship Engine Room Simulator	no		nophoto.png	Lower than 50% used	no		Samet	BICEN	Research Assistant	Marine Engineering	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Digitalization - Advanced material science and engineering/artificial intelligence - Digitalization - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
13056618	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Model making	Industrial Design Application Workshop	Model making and prototyping workshop especially for the industrial design students. Besides the traditional tools, there are also modern equipment.	no		nophoto.png	Almost fully used	yes		Fayza	ERGÜN		Model making	X		Connectivity - Culture creativity and inclusive society/Connectivity - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Teaching activities.		
13048273	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Architecture	Innovation and Modeling Laboratory	Innovation and Modeling Laboratory is a laboratory with education and research priority. In the field of architecture, studies are carried out to research, develop and test design, production and evaluation tools. In the laboratory, activities open to undergraduates and graduate students are organized for educational purposes on certain dates. Students who want to carry out their research in the laboratory should apply to the laboratory supervisor with the Scientific Research Project (BAP) documents with the approval of the coordinators. The usage area is 150 m ² ; production, warehouse and working areas are divided into three. The devices in the laboratory are: CNC (1), 3D printer (1).	yes	https://mim.itu.edu.tr/mv-laboratuvar/	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	yes		Süheyla Müge	HALICI	Laboratory Coordinator	Architecture	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility/artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching activities		
12989229	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Electronics and Communication Engineering Department	Introduction to Electronics Laboratory	DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter	yes	https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/	12920506.jpg	Almost fully used	yes	https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/Labkullurari.pdf	İbrahim	CATALKAYA		Electronics and Communication Engineering Department	X		Advanced material science and engineering	Teaching activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/Labkullurari.pdf	

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13168153	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		ITU Smart Grid Lab	ITU Smart Grid Lab	In the ITU Smart Grid Laboratory, we focus on developing ideas and methods using advanced computational intelligence, systems & control theory, and signal processing techniques to facilitate a secure, reliable, and efficient operation of electric power systems in the smart grid environment. Our research scope includes the secure, optimal operation and control of electric power systems ranging from small-scale low voltage distribution systems, microgrids, to large interconnected high voltage transmission systems.	yes	https://smartgrid.itu.edu.tr/	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Istemihan	GENC		ITU Smart Grid Lab	X		Artificial intelligence - Smart industry and space technologies Artificial intelligence - Smart industry and space technologies	Research activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...) - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
13055317	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		hydrodynamics	ITU-KAT (Istanbul Technical University Cavitation Tunnel)	A large scale cavitation tunnel for hydroacoustic research	no		nophoto.png	Almost fully used	no		Ugur Oral	UNAL		hydrodynamics	X		Advanced material science and engineering Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
11651941	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Dept. of Mechanical Eng.	Laboratory of Biomechanics and Strength of Materials	Stress Analysis +) Numerical And Theoretical +) Experimental Structural Analysis (Dynamics & Static) Structural Testing & Fatigue Material Characterization +) Static +) Strain-Rate Dependent (Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar) Vibration and Noise Analysis TSI Type Approval - Design Analysis & Testing - of Rolling Stock (&Bogies) +) In close cooperation with numerous Notified Bodies Biomechanics +) Modeling and Numerical Analysis +) Experimental Stress & Kinematic Analysis +) Development of Experimental Methods	no		nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Enin	SUNBULOGLU	Laboratory Correspondent	Dept. of Mechanical Eng.	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences	Research, and others (industrial...)	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
12944133	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Control and Automation Engineering	Measurement, Instrumentation and Control Laboratory	Equipment/Used For DIGIAC 1750 Transducers & Instrumentation Training Systems (9 Units)Experimental introduction to comprehensive transducer to input and output transducers, signal conditioning circuits and display devices. Used for laboratory sessions of the courses Measurement and Sensors and Electronic Instrumentation. Quanser Helicopter SystemThe helicopter system with 3 degrees of freedom is a simplified helicopter model. In this system, the aim is to design a control system to regulate and follow the elevation and travel angles.Graduation projects and research purposes. Quanser Paper Wrapping SystemThe Paper Wrapping system is the model of the systems used in the industrial paper printing house. In this system, the aim is to design a controller that wraps and unloads the paper at the desired speed and tension. Graduation projects and research purposes. Ball & Beam Experiment SetThe ball-beam system practically corresponds to the problem of controlling the angle of rotation of aircraft. In this system, the aim is to design a cascade control structure to stabilize the ball. An experiment of Control Laboratory course. Fan and plate control systemThe control objective is by blowing an airstream at the plate with a variable speed fan. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.	yes	https://kontrol.itu.edu.tr/en/research/laboratories/measurement-instrumentation-and-process-control-laboratory	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no			Yaprak	YALÇIN	Laboratory	Dept. of Mechanical Eng.	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies	Research, Teaching activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
11649925	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		MEMS Research Center	MEMS Research Center	The size of MEMS clean room is 100 m ² and its classification is class 1000. The ambient of the cleanroom is controlled so that R.H and temperature are 50% and 20°C, respectively. The service and supporting units cover 150 m ² , please take a look at both the cell lab and the clean room image galleries below. The clean-room has the wet/dry etch capability and PVD-based deposition system. There are also several tools for the characterization of microsystems. There are several simulation tools as well, the important ones are Comsol MEMS module and ANSYS programs. Besides, there is a cell laboratory for cell based studies which is annexed to the MEMS Center. Cell Culture laboratory was founded in 2015 to perform biological applications using microfluidic systems. Cell lines used in mechanobiology and cell separation studies are cultivated in this laboratory in order to carry-out the experiments effectively. We have also access to the ITU Nano Nanotechnology Research Center. If needed, please take a look at www.nano.itu.edu.tr for the equipment available there. Note: Some equipment may be out of order. Please contact us first to check.	yes	www.memsi.itu.edu.tr/	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Levent	TRABZON	Director	MEMS Research Center	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration	
12910673	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Turkish Natural Language Processing	Natural Language Processing Lab	Different databases related to languages	yes	https://nlp.itu.edu.tr/	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Gülşen	ERYİĞİT	Assoc. Prof. Dr., Vice Chair of the AI & Data Engineering Dep. Director of TURKISH TEACHING APPLICATION AND RESEARCH	Turkish Natural Language Processing	X	X	Artificial intelligence Artificial intelligence	Research activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)	
12920508	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter	Supply voltage schemes, DC characteristics of BJT and MOSFET, transistor amplifiers, linear applications of OPAMPs	DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter	yes	https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/indexenglish.html	12920508.jpg	Almost fully used	no		Bora	DOKEN	Lecturer	DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter	X		Advanced material science and engineering	Teaching activities		

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13060963	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		University	Sustainable & Green Plastics Laboratory (SGPL)	We have devices for Polymer Processing and characterisation: Twin Screw Extruder GÜLNAR, GM TWIN 16 mm, L/D 30:1 Equipped with cooling bath and pelletizer Single Screw Extruder ENFORMAK Equipped with cooling bath and monofilament drawer Micro-compounder Haake MiniLab Equipped with co-rotating and counter-rotating twin screws Internal Mixt Mixer Kökbr RTx-M40 Capacity 40 gr Microcellular Batch Foaming Setup Equipped with TeleDyne ISCO Model 200HP Syringe Pump. Compression Mold MSE-PRESS-SERIES Rotational Rheometer, Anton Paar MCR 301 Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC), TA Instruments Q1000 Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA), SII 6000 Extra TGD/TA 6300 X-ray diffractometer (XRD), Phase Model PW3710 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), JEOL 7600 FEG	yes	https://sgpl.itu.edu.tr	nophoto.png	Between 50% to 80% used	yes	ISO 17025	Mohammadreza	NOPAR	Lab Manager	University	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering/Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching activities	
12908107	Istanbul Technical University (ITU)	An open teaching laboratory		Textile and Apparel Quality Control and Research Laboratory	Textile and Apparel Quality Control and Research Laboratory	Physical and chemical tests and analyzes for textile materials performed in our laboratories are the following: Physical Test / Analysis for Fiber - Yam Physical Testing/Analysis for Fabrica Chemical Testing/Analysis Fastness Tests Washing Tests	yes	https://teklab.itu.edu.tr/	nophoto.png	Almost fully used	yes	ISO 17025	Umut Kivanc	SAHIN	Lab Manager	Textile and Apparel Quality Control and Research Laboratory	X		Advanced material science and engineering/Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	ISO 17025
11642279	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	The Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory mainly targets the engineering of an artificial tactile sense in parallel to the investigation of human touch. We develop and integrate novel transducers, both synthetic and bio-hybrid. We implement neuromorphic systems, with natural spiking coding of tactile information. We analyse neural data to unveil the neuronal processes underlying the human sense of touch, and we implement behavioural protocols to characterize the perception of tactile features. This body of neuroscientific knowledge and the developed birobotic technologies converge in a key application domain in upper limb neuroprosthetics, with complementary interests stemming towards safe human-machine co-work, tele-presence for medical robotics and hand-held consumer	yes	https://www.santannapia.it/en/institute/birobotics/visiting-opportunities	nophoto.png	Almost fully used	yes	https://www.santannapia.it/en/institute/birobotics/visiting-opportunities	Calogero	ODDO	Associate Professor, Head of Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences/Artificial intelligence - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.santannapia.it/en/institute/birobotics/visiting-opportunities
11597019	Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)	An open teaching laboratory		STG - Polvani	Laboratorio di Storia, Archeologia, Epigrafia, Tradizione dell'Antico	The SAET Laboratory is duly equipped for managing every step in the documentation of structures, contexts, and items retrieved during field research. Among the shooting equipment for aerial photography, besides the usual telescopic poles, a UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) is often used to take both digital and infra-red images. Aerial stereophotographic pictures are processed to produce the 3D models necessary to create orthophotos for scientific purposes and other materials for scientific dissemination. A digital microscope allows for the documentation of details from inscriptions, coins and sherds. Traditional drawing equipment includes a total station and wire pantographs. The SAET is fitted for producing good resin replicas of inscriptions and other items (the replicas of inscriptions from Segesta exhibited in the Palazzo della Carovana at the Scuola Normale Superiore are a good example).	yes	https://saet.sns.it/it/	11597019.jpg	Between 50% to 80% used	no		Alessandro	CORRETTI	Responsible Operativo	STG - Polvani	X		Social sciences and humanities	Research, Teaching activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA - For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level) - For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
11571273	Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)	An open teaching laboratory		Laboratorio NEST	Laboratorio NEST	The Laboratorio NEST facilities offer a wide spectrum of tools for your research needs.	yes	www.laboratorio.nest.it	11571273.jpg	Almost fully used	yes	https://www.laboratorio.nest.it/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2/Richiesta_da_ENTE_a_NEST_ENG_rev4.do	Pasqualantonio	PINGUE	Chief Operating Officer	Laboratorio NEST	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.laboratorionest.it/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2/Richiesta_da_ENTE_a_NEST_ENG_rev4.do
11598205	Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)	An open teaching laboratory		Classe di Lettere e Filosofia	SAET	The SAET Laboratory is duly equipped for managing every step in the documentation of structures, contexts, and items retrieved during field research. Among the shooting equipment for aerial photography, besides the usual telescopic poles, a UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) is often used to take both digital and infra-red images. Aerial stereophotographic pictures are processed to produce the 3D models necessary to create orthophotos for scientific purposes and other materials for scientific dissemination. A digital microscope allows for the documentation of details from inscriptions, coins and sherds. Traditional drawing equipment includes a total station and wire pantographs. The SAET is fitted for producing good resin replicas of inscriptions and other items (the replicas of inscriptions from Segesta exhibited in the Palazzo della Carovana at the Scuola Normale Superiore are a good example).	yes	https://saet.sns.it/it/	11598205.jpg	Almost fully used	no		Gianfranco	ADORNATO	Associate Professor	Classe di Lettere e Filosofia	X		Digitalization - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research activities	Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA - For teaching purposes within EELISA
421	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Group of Optics Photonics and Biotónica (GOFB)	3D printer	Impresora 3D ULTIMAKER 2	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/impresora-3d/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/537	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/impresora-3d/	Miguel	HOLGADO BOLAÑOS	Responsible	Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biotónica (GOFB); CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/impresora-3d/	
291	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Turkish Natural Language Processing	AB200 Laser microprocessin g	Diferent databases related to languages	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-ab200	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/186	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-ab200	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	Turkish Natural Language Processing	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-ab200/	
341	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	Accelerated extraction ASE-200	Equipo de extracción acelerada (ASE-200)	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/equipo-de-extraccion-acelerada-ase-200	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/288	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/equipo-de-extraccion-acelerada-ase-200/	Jose Eugenio	ORTIZ MENEDEZ	Responsible	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/equipo-de-extraccion-acelerada-ase-200/	
230	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Activated steam sianlization equipment	Este equipo usa la técnica AIVS (Activated Vapor Sianlization, Sianlización por vapor activado) para la formación de una lámina delgada de espesor submicrométrico con una alta densidad de grupos funcionales. Dependiendo del precursor organometálico se puede controlar el grupo funcional superficial final.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/equipo-de-sianlizacion-por-vapor-activado/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/548	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/equipo-de-sianlizacion-por-vapor-activado/	Gustavo Víctor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/equipo-de-sianlizacion-por-vapor-activado/	
47	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)			Marine Engineering	Aerodynamic tunnel S4	Túnel aerodinámico para calibración de anemómetros	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/tunel-aerodinamico-s4/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/439	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/tunel-aerodinamico-s4/	Angel Pedro	SANZ ANDRES	Responsible	Marine Engineering	X	X	Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infaestructura/tunel-aerodinamico-s4/	

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486	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	AI Image Analysis platform	Plataforma de análisis de imagen por medio de métodos de inteligencia artificial. Cuenta con alta capacidad de computación, almacenamiento y procesamiento de imágenes.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-de-imagen/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/626			https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-de-imagen/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-de-imagen/
485	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	AI platform for descriptive and prescriptive analysis of clinical data	Plataforma con capacidad de procesamiento y análisis de datos desde un punto de vista estadístico, así como de la aplicación de enfoques de machine learning (aprendizaje automático) a niveles descriptivo y predictivo sobre grandes volúmenes de datos clínicos. Se hace uso de sensores de alto rendimiento para la computación y entrenamiento de modelos en base a la aplicación de algoritmos de inteligencia artificial.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-analisis-descriptivo-y-predictivo-de-datos-clinicos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/625		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-analisis-descriptivo-y-predictivo-de-datos-clinicos/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-descriptivo-y-predictivo-de-datos-clinicos/
459	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Animal lab	El animalario del CTB tiene una superficie de 55 m ² ; la superficie interior útil total es de 30m ² , distribuidos de la siguiente forma: - Dos zonas independientes para la estabulación de roedores. - Zona de cuarentena. - Vestíbulo. - Pequeño almacén con capacidad de fungibles para una semana de funcionamiento. - Zona experimental de laboratorio para quidanos y estudios de comportamiento. - Zona de instalaciones. La instalación proporciona un ambiente controlado para los animales, con control periódico de dieta, agua, temperatura, aire, ciclo de luz/oscuridad natural, condiciones de vivienda y manejo, además del control de la calidad microbiológica y genética de los animales utilizados en la experimentación rutinaria y exámenes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/animalario/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/592		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/animalario/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/animalario/
508	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Radiation research group	Antena Testing and Homologation Laboratory (LEHA)	LEHA (Laboratorio de Ensayos y Homologación de Antenas) ha estado trabajando en Mediciones de Antena desde 1980 para actividades industriales, investigación y fines educativos, y está incluido en el Grupo de Radiación (GR) del Departamento de SSR de la UPM. El director de calidad de LEHA es el Prof. Manuel Sierra Castañer y la directora técnica es la Prof. Belén Galocha Iragien. El personal de LEHA está formado por el ingeniero Pablo Caballero, el ingeniero Xiaoliang Sun y el técnico Cristian Martínez. Un número variable de estudiantes de tesis de maestría también colabora en LEHA. LEHA se reorganiza con la acreditación ISO 17025 para la medición de antenas. LEHA está incluido en la red RLA de la iniciativa Madrid+ (Comunidad de Madrid).	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/leha-laboratorio-de-ensayos-y-homologacion-de-antenas/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/634		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/leha-laboratorio-de-ensayos-y-homologacion-de-antenas/	Manuel	SIERRA CASTAÑER	Responsible	Grupo: Grupo de Radiación; Centro/int. Centro de I+D+i en Procesado de la Información y Telecomunicaciones (PIT)	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/leha-laboratorio-de-ensayos-y-homologacion-de-antenas/
278	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) with liquid cell	El equipo dispone de 8 piezoeléctricos independientes, control Dualscan®, software WSAI, celda líquida y posicionador XY. Permite realizar toma de imágenes AFM en modo contacto, jumping, topográfico y dinámico (modulación de amplitud y modulación de frecuencia); medidas espectroscópicas de 2 (FZ), 3 (3D-Mode) y 4 (General Spectroscopy Imaging) incluyendo Force Volume) dimensiones; medidas de larga distancia con método de doble pasada (retrace) y escaneo de un plano (plane scan). También incluye corrección automática de drift. Además, dispone de un sistema de intercambio de líquido que permite controlar las condiciones físico-químicas del medio en el que se encuentran las muestras. El equipo se encuentra acoplado a un microscopio óptico invertido lo que permite el posicionamiento del elemento sensor en	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-de-fuerza-atomica-afm-con-celda-liquida/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/588		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-de-fuerza-atomica-afm-con-celda-liquida/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-de-fuerza-atomica-afm-con-celda-liquida/
425	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		mFINE and Spanish Centre for nutrition and physical activity	Biochemicals Improvement (of health) by fitness, nutrition and physical activity	El laboratorio cuenta con un autocalentador de muestras, fotómetro de llama, lector de placas ELISA, microscopio óptico, congelador (hasta -80 ₂), centrifuga y contador de células.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioquimica/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/547		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioquimica/	Maria Marcela	GONZALEZ GROSS	Responsible	Grupo: Grupo de Investigación en nutrición, ejercicio y estilo de vida	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioquimica/
442	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Bioinformatics Support Unit (BSU)	Servicio de Análisis Bioinformáticos	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/unidad-de-soporte-bioinformatico-bsu/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/807		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/unidad-de-soporte-bioinformatico-bsu/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsible	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-plátano; Centro/int. Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la Planta	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/unidad-de-soporte-bioinformatico-bsu/
329	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Machines engineering research group	Bioprinter	Biopresora Inkredible de Cellink	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/biopresora/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/238		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/biopresora/	Jose Luis	MUÑOZ SANZ	Responsible	Grupo: GI-IMI: Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería de Máquinas	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/biopresora/
579	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Bioscreen	Sistema miniaturizado de monitorización de crecimiento microbiano	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/bioscreen/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/800		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/bioscreen/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsible	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-plátano; Centro/int. Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la Planta	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/bioscreen/
484	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Marine Engineering	Cell culture unit	Unidad de Cultivos Celulares dotada con equipamiento para la realización de experimentación con diferentes modelos de líneas celulares de origen animal, incluyendo las líneas celulares de origen humano. A Unidad se compone de un laboratorio de nivel de contención biológica 1 (NCB1), un laboratorio de nivel de contención biológica 2 (NCB2) y una zona de lavado y esterilización común. El laboratorio NCB1 está formado por: Una cabina de flujo laminar horizontal TELSTAR 3 incubadores de CO2 Thermo con sensor de infrarrojo y camisa de agua de 80 L y un incubador CO2 Lab-Line para el mantenimiento de cultivos celulares. Un lector de placas por absorbancia Una centrifuga refrigerada Hettich Rotina Un congelador hasta -80°C Una nevera con rango de temperaturas entre -4 y 20°C 2 cabinas de flujo laminar vertical clase II Nuairte El laboratorio NCB2 está formado por: Una cabina de flujo laminar clase II Nuairte Un incubador CO2 Thermo Scientific 3111 W ater Jacket con sensor de infrarrojo y camisa de agua de 80 L Una centrifuga HERMLE Z38 Un	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/unidad-de-cultivos-celulares/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/600		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/unidad-de-cultivos-celulares/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Marine Engineering	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/unidad-de-cultivos-celulares/
581	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Institute of nuclear fusion	Coating manufacturing	Equipo de pulverización catódica equipado con dos imanes circulares (Ø=5cm) y un portamuestras giratorio conectado a diversas líneas de gases (Ar, N y O)	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/fabricacion-de-recubrimientos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/811		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/fabricacion-de-recubrimientos/	Pedro	VELARDE MAYOL	Responsible	Grupo: Fusión Nuclear de fusión; Centro/int. Instituto de Fusión Nuclear Guillermo Velarde	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/fabricacion-de-recubrimientos/
482	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Cognitive rehabilitation platform	Guttmann. NeuroPersonalTrainer® (GNPT6) es un dispositivo médico comercial de rehabilitación cognitiva de pacientes en domicilio.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-cognitiva/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/728		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-cognitiva/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-cognitiva/
215	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Laser centre	Confocal microscopy	Microscopía Confocal. Microscopio Leica DCM 3D Sistema para la adquisición de imágenes en 3D de la morfología de la muestra.-Objetivos Confocales: 10X, 20X, 50X, 100X-Objetivos Interferométrico: 50X Mirau	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopia-confocal/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/567		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopia-confocal/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int. Centro Láser	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopia-confocal/
556	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Digital microscope with polarizer	Microscopio digital con polarizador Dino-Line AM41152HW con conexión USB, resolución de 1.3 Mega píxeles y tasa de aumento de 10x a 50x.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-digital-con-polarizador/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/749		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-digital-con-polarizador/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsible	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-digital-con-polarizador/

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476	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for biomedical technology	DL S measuring equipment	El equipo permite medir el tamaño molecular y de partícula de 0.3 a 10 µm, medir el potencial Z de partículas y moléculas a través de Dispersión de Luz Electroforética (ELS) indicando la estabilidad de la muestra y/o la propensión a agregarse. Cuenta además con una rueda de filtros ópticos con filtro de fluorescencia para permitir la medida de muestras fluorescentes sin perjudicar la sensibilidad del sistema. Incluye además filtros de polarización (horizontales o verticales) para medidas de tipo DDLS (Depolarized Dynamic Light Scattering).	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-medicion-mediante-dispersion-dinamica-de-luz/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/688		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-medicion-mediante-dispersion-dinamica-de-luz/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO		Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-medicion-mediante-dispersion-dinamica-de-luz/
427	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Laboratory of Exercise Physiology Research Group.	Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA)	Absorciometría dual de rayos X (DXA) para realización de densitometrías óseas.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/absorciometria-dual-de-rayos-x-dxa/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/662		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/absorciometria-dual-de-rayos-x-dxa/	Ana Belen PEINADO LOZANO		Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Investigación del Laboratorio de Fisiología del Esfuerzo.	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/absorciometria-dual-de-rayos-x-dxa/
536	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Biomechanical analysis Group	Dynamometric platforms	Sistema de medida bilateral de las fuerzas de reacción y del equilibrio de pie que permite medir las fuerzas de reacción en el apoyo y el punto de aplicación de la carga.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/plataformas-dinamicas/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/719		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/plataformas-dinamicas/	Enrique NAVARRO CABELLO		Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/plataformas-dinamicas/
524	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials	EBS detector for crystallographic analysis of metal samples	Detector Bruker Quantax EBSD 400 con áreas de detección activas desde 10mm ² hasta 100cm ² . Resolución nativa de al menos 640x400 píxeles, preferida de 1600x1200 píxeles.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/detector-ebsd-para-analisis-cristalografico-de-muestras-metali/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/695		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/detector-ebsd-para-analisis-cristalografico-de-muestras-metali/	Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ		Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Investigación en Materiales	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/detector-ebsd-para-analisis-cristalografico-de-muestras-metali/
441	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Control and Automation Engineering	Equipment for analysis of nuclear acid integrity and quality (Tapestation)	Equipment Used For DIGIAC 1750 Transducers & Instrumentation Training Systems (8 Units) Experimental introduction to comprehensive transducer to input and output transducers, signal conditioning circuits and display devices. Used for laboratory sessions of the courses Measurement and Sensors and Electronic Instrumentation. Quanser Helicopter System The helicopter system with 3 degrees of freedom is a simplified helicopter model. In this system, the aim is to design a control system to regulate and follow the elevation and travel angles. Graduation project and research purposes. Quanser Paper Wrapping System The Paper Wrapping system is the model of the systems used in the industrial paper printing house. In this system, the aim is to design a controller that wraps and unloads the paper at the desired speed and tension. Graduation projects and research purposes. Ball & Beam Experiment Set The ball-beam system practically corresponds to the problem of controlling the angle of rotation of aircraft. In this system, the aim is to design a cascade control structure to stabilize the ball. An experiment of Control Laboratory course. Fan and plate control system The control objective is the angular orientation of a hinge rectangular plate and the control means is by blowing an airstream at	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-para-analisis-de-la-integridad-y-calidad-de-acidos-nucleicos-tapestation/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/792		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-para-analisis-de-la-integridad-y-calidad-de-acidos-nucleicos-tapestation/	Antonio FERNANDEZ		Responsable	Control and Automation Engineering	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-para-analisis-de-la-integridad-y-calidad-de-acidos-nucleicos-tapestation/
481	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for biomedical technology	Equipment for dynamic characterization of viscosity of biological fluids	El sensor VISQCT es un dispositivo desarrollado en el Laboratorio de Bioinstrumentación y Nanomedicina para medir la viscosidad de un fluido utilizando un volumen reducido (50 µl aproximadamente). Su funcionamiento se basa en la utilización de Resonadores de Cristal de Cuarzo (QCR por sus siglas en inglés) los cuales son elementos económicos, pequeños y precisos. Los QCR utilizados son con electrodos de oro y con frecuencia de resonancia fundamental de 10 MHz. El dispositivo consta del circuito electrónico, resonadores de cristal de cuarzo, holder del cristal, baterías y software de	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-caracterizacion-dinamica-de-viscosidad-en-fluidos-biologicos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/658		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-caracterizacion-dinamica-de-viscosidad-en-fluidos-biologicos/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO		Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-caracterizacion-dinamica-de-viscosidad-en-fluidos-biologicos/
460	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for biomedical technology	Equipment for extracellular electrophysiology	Técnica que realiza registros de actividad eléctrica de cultivos celulares con alta resolución temporal y espacial. Servicio de electrofisiología extracelular mediante el sistema de arrays de microelectrodos de Multichannel Systems MEA 2100.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/594		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO		Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/
573	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Equipment for high sensitivity image acquisition (FluimaZone)	Microscopio estereoscópico LEICA M205FA de fluorescencia y bioluminiscencia	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipamiento-de-captacion-de-imagenes-de-alta-sensibilidad-flumazone/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/793		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipamiento-de-captacion-de-imagenes-de-alta-sensibilidad-flumazone/	Antonio FERNANDEZ		Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógenos; Centro/int. Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de las plantas	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipamiento-de-captacion-de-imagenes-de-alta-sensibilidad-flumazone/
420	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Group of Optics Photonics and Biotonics (GOFB)	Equipment for photolithography y MA6 with mask projection	EQUIPO DE LITOGRAFIA M46 CON POSIBILIDAD DE ACOPLE DE SISTEMA DE NANOPRESION SUSS MA6	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/m46-fotolitografia-por-proyeccion-de-mascara/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/534		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/m46-fotolitografia-por-proyeccion-de-mascara/	Miguel BOLANOS		Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Óptica F50niza y Biotonics (GOFB); Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/m46-fotolitografia-por-proyeccion-de-mascara/
454	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	Equipment for ray diffraction for analysis of mineral components Rigaku Miniflex 600	Equipo de difracción de rayos-X para análisis de componentes minerales	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-difraccion-de-rayos-x-para-analisis-de-componentes-minerales-rigaku-miniflex-600/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/642		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-difraccion-de-rayos-x-para-analisis-de-componentes-minerales-rigaku-miniflex-600/	Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENEDEZ		Responsable	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-difraccion-de-rayos-x-para-analisis-de-componentes-minerales-rigaku-miniflex-600/
512	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Laboratory of Exercise Physiology Research Group.	Exercise physiology Lab (LFE)	Laboratorio de docencia e investigación en el campo de la Fisiología del Ejercicio que cuenta con distintos equipos como para la medición y evaluación de la condición física, como cicloergómetro, para pruebas de esfuerzo en tapiz rodante, equipo de medición de lactato y analizador portátil de gases.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/laboratorio-de-fisiologia-del-esfuerzo-lfe/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/664		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/laboratorio-de-fisiologia-del-esfuerzo-lfe/	Ana Belen PEINADO LOZANO		Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Investigación del Laboratorio de Fisiología del Esfuerzo.	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/laboratorio-de-fisiologia-del-esfuerzo-lfe/
521	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials	FDM Fortus 450mc printer for polymeric material and thread material	Impresora de material polimérico y compuesto por hilo tecnología FDM. Piezas con calidad industrial. Capacidad para uso con distintos materiales plásticos ABS-M30, ABS-M30, ABS-ESD7, ASA, PC-ABS, PC, PC-ISO, Nylon 12, ULTEM 9085, ULTEM 1010, ST130, Nylon12CF, ANTERO 300NA (bajo disponibilidad de filament). Tamaño de fabricación de 40x65x450mm.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/impresora-de-material-polimerico-y-compuesto-por-hilo-tecnologia-fdm-fortus-450mc/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/689		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/impresora-de-material-polimerico-y-compuesto-por-hilo-tecnologia-fdm-fortus-450mc/	Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ		Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/impresora-de-material-polimerico-y-compuesto-por-hilo-tecnologia-fdm-fortus-450mc/
503	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Fiber synthesis equipment through Spinning Flow Spinning (SFS)	Producción de fibras biocompatibles de altas prestaciones de propiedades controladas. SFS es un método de producción versátil y asequible de fibras regeneradas (producidas con proteínas naturales) y biopirridas (producidas con proteínas recombinantes) para producir fibras que combina la biocompatibilidad y el altas prestaciones mecánicas.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-sintesis-de-fibras-por-straining-flow-spinning-sfs/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/img/668		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-sintesis-de-fibras-por-straining-flow-spinning-sfs/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO		Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int. Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructural/equipo-de-sintesis-de-fibras-por-straining-flow-spinning-sfs/

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414	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Group of Optics Photonics and Biobotronics (GOFB)	Filmetrics	Sistema de medida de espesores e índices de refracción con lámpara halógena	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/filmetrics/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/529		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/filmetrics/	Miguel	HOLCAJO BOLAÑOS	Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biotónica (GOFB); CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomedica	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/filmetrics/
558	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Fuel Cells and alternative fuels lab	Laboratorio con una superficie de 60 m ² equipado con agua corriente, tomas de corriente monofásica de 220 V a 50 Hz y tomas de corriente trifásica de 380 V a 50 Hz.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/774		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsable	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos/
337	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (6890/5973)	Cromatógrafo de gases/espectrómetro de masas (6890/5973)	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-gases-espectrometro-de-masas-6890-5973/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/530		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-gases-espectrometro-de-masas-6890-5973/	Jose Eugenio	ORTIZ MENEDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-gases-espectrometro-de-masas-6890-5973/
10	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Turkish Natural Language Processing	Gas mass	Different databases related to languages	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/gases-masas/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/10		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/gases-masas/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Turkish Natural Language Processing	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/gases-masas/
559	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Design and manufacturing engineering	Goniometer for measuring contact angles	Goniómetro para medir ángulos de contacto de contrucción propia	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/goniometro-para-medir-angulos-de-contacto/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/757		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/goniometro-para-medir-angulos-de-contacto/	Jose Manuel	ARENAS REINA	Responsable	Grupo: Diseño y fabricación industrial; CentroInt: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/goniometro-para-medir-angulos-de-contacto/
361	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Biodiversity and conservation of plant genetic resources	Green Classroom - Educational Greenhouse	Invernadero de exhibición, catedrático y con sistema de riego automático. Dispone de un taller de propagación de plantas. En una superficie de 300 m ² alberga una colección de más de 200 especies botánicas.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/aula-verde-invernadero-didactico-av/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/327		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/aula-verde-invernadero-didactico-av/	Juan Pedro	MARTIN CLEMENTE	Responsable	Grupo: Biodiversidad y conservación de recursos fitogenéticos	X	X	Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/aula-verde-invernadero-didactico-av/
416	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Greenhouses (modules) of the Centre for Plant Biotechnology and Genomics	Invernadero (Módulos) del CBGP	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/invernadero-modulos-del-cbpg/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/552		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/invernadero-modulos-del-cbpg/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; CentroInt: Centro de Biología y Genómica de la Planta	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/invernadero-modulos-del-cbpg/
548	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Heated plates hydraulic press	Prensa hidráulica MASINOX modelo MGH-30 de platos calientes de 300 mm x 300 mm con capacidad de compresión de hasta 600 kg/cm ² , regulación de temperatura hasta 250 °C y configuración de ciclo térmico. Refrigeración por agua.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/prensa-hidraulica-de-platos-calientes/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/732		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/prensa-hidraulica-de-platos-calientes/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsable	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/prensa-hidraulica-de-platos-calientes/
338	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC-1100)	Cromatógrafo de líquidos de altas prestaciones (HPLC-1100) con detector de fluorescencia y diodo-array	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-liquidos-de-altas-prestaciones-hplc-1100/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/597		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-liquidos-de-altas-prestaciones-hplc-1100/	Jose Eugenio	ORTIZ MENEDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-liquidos-de-altas-prestaciones-hplc-1100/
510	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Plant Biotechnology	Human cell cultures lab	Laboratorio completo compuesto por 2 cabinas de flujo laminar vertical, un incubador de células, un microscopio invertido y otros equipos auxiliares que permiten cultivar líneas celulares humanas creando las condiciones necesarias para su crecimiento y manipulación segura.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivos-celulares/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/640		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivos-celulares/	Isabel Marta	ALLONA ALBERICH	Responsable	Grupo: Biotecnología Vegetal; CentroInt: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la planta	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivos-celulares-humanos/
488	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Electronic and microelectronic design group	Hyperspectral camera Headwall E-series SWIR Push-Broom	Cámara móvil con las siguientes características de número de bandas y espectro: 267 bandas, 900-2500 nm, 640 x N	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-headwall-e-series-swir-push-broom/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/674		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-headwall-e-series-swir-push-broom/	Cesar	SANZ ALVARO	Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Diseño Electrónico y Microelectrónico; CentroInt: Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías Software y Sistemas Multimedia para Sostenibilidad	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-headwall-e-series-swir-push-broom/
486	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Electronic and microelectronic design group	Hyperspectral camera Headwall E-series VNIR Push-Broom	Cámara móvil con las siguientes características de número de bandas y espectro: 369 bandas, 400-1000 nm, 1600 x N	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-headwall-e-series-vnir-push-broom/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/679		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-headwall-e-series-vnir-push-broom/	Cesar	SANZ ALVARO	Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Diseño Electrónico y Microelectrónico; CentroInt: Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías Software y Sistemas Multimedia para Sostenibilidad	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-headwall-e-series-vnir-push-broom/
485	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Electronic and microelectronic design group	Hyperspectral camera Ximea Snapshot	El grupo dispone de 4 cámaras móviles con las siguientes características de número de bandas y espectro: 25 bandas, 665-975 nm y 2045 x 1085 (400 x 217).	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-ximea-snapshot/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/671		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-ximea-snapshot/	Cesar	SANZ ALVARO	Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Diseño Electrónico y Microelectrónico; CentroInt: Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías Software y Sistemas Multimedia para Sostenibilidad	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/camara-hiperspectral-ximea-snapshot/
66	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Model making	Impact simulation system	Sistema para realizar ensayos de choque, evaluar la seguridad pasiva de los vehículos y evaluar el nivel de protección ofrecido a sus pasajeros.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/simulador-de-impactos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/550		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/simulador-de-impactos/	Jose Maria	LOPEZ MARTINEZ	Responsable	Model making	X	X	Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/simulador-de-impactos/
509	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Plant Biotechnology	Infrastructure for biomarkers and allergen detection and quantification	La infraestructura está compuesta por sistemas electroforéticos, lector de microplacas y espectrofotómetros.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-deteccion-y-cuantificacion-de-alergenos-y-biomarcadores/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/538		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-deteccion-y-cuantificacion-de-alergenos-y-biomarcadores/	Isabel Marta	ALLONA ALBERICH	Responsable	Grupo: Biotecnología Vegetal; CentroInt: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la planta	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-deteccion-y-cuantificacion-de-alergenos-y-biomarcadores/
210	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Laser centre	Inolas Laser microprocessig	Sistema preparado para realizar procesos de microprocesado láser usando óptica fija o escanar y pudiendo trabajar en distintas longitudes de onda (IR, VIS, UV).	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-inolas/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/566		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-inolas/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsable	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; CentroInt: Centro Láser	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-inolas/

INFRA_ID	INFRA_UNIV	INFRA_TYPE	INFRA_DVT	INFRA_RS	INFRA_NAME	INFRA_DESC	WEBSITE_EXI ST	WEBSITE	PHOTO	INFRA_LO AD	SHARE_EXI TING_RULE	SHARE_LINK	CONTACT_NA ME	CONTACT_LA ST_NAME	CONTACT_PO SITION	CONTACT_RS	AGREE_MAPP NG	AGREE_CATA LOG	INFRA_DOMAINS	INFRA_TEACH RESEAR	SHARE
533	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		hydrodynamics	Laboratory for fuel cells and alternative fuels with flame capboard	Laboratorio con una superficie de 46m2 equipado con campana de gases de alto flujo, agua corriente y poyatas de trabajo con tomas de corriente de 220 V a 50 Hz.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos-con-campana-de-gases/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/743		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos-con-campana-de-gases/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsible	hydrodynamics	X	X	Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos-con-campana-de-gases/
533	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Radiation research group	Laptop 3D printer	La impresora 3D de Form 3 del fabricante estadounidense Formlabs, es la evolución de su ya conocida Form 2, elegida entre las mejores impresoras 3D de resina. La impresora 3D tiene una tecnología de impresión: la Low Force Stereolithography (LFS), una tecnología un sistema a medida de láseres y espejos para polimerizar la resina fotosensibilizada. De acuerdo al fabricante, gracias a esta tecnología se puede fabricar 4 veces más rápido y con mayor	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/impresora-3d-de-escriptorio-modelo-form-3-de-formlabs/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/722	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/impresora-3d-de-escriptorio-modelo-form-3-de-formlabs/	Manuel	SIERRA CASTAÑER	Responsible	Grupo: Grupo de Radiación; CentroInt: Centro de I+D+i en el Proceso de la Información y Telecomunicaciones	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/impresora-3d-de-escriptorio-modelo-form-3-de-formlabs/	
229	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Electronics and Communication Engineering Department	Laser Lumera Super Rapid	DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laser-lumera-super-rapid/	1290506.jpg	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laser-lumera-super-rapid/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	Electronics and Communication Engineering Department	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laser-lumera-super-rapid/
526	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Laser centre	Laser nano and micromanufacturing lab	El Laboratorio de Micro y Nanofabricación con láser cuenta con todo el equipamiento necesario para el estudio, parametrización y ejecución de procesos láser con tolerancias dimensionales en el rango micro y submicrométrico en cualquier tipo de material. En la actualidad el Servicio cuenta con fuentes láseres pulsadas en fs con ancho de pulso programable a 1030 nm (EKSPLA FemtoLux 30), ps a 355nm, 532 nm y 1064 nm (LUMERA Super Rapid y Spectra Physics Vanguard) así como varias fuentes de ns a 355, 532 y 1064 nm (incluida una fuente de alta potencia en UV, de alta potencia en UV). Todos los láseres están integrados en máquinas o bancadas de proceso y se dispone de escáneres, sistemas de control y conformado de haz y diferentes sistemas de enfoque para poder utilizar cualquier estrategia de irradiación del material y simular condiciones de proceso en entornos productivos. El servicio dispone también de la instrumentación necesaria para la caracterización de los procesos in situ, incluyendo Microscopio SEM Hitachi 3000N, Microscopio Confocal e Interferométrico Leica DCM 3D y Microscopio	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-micro-y-nanofabricacion-con-laser/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/705	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-micro-y-nanofabricacion-con-laser/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; CentroInt: Centro Láser	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-micro-y-nanofabricacion-con-laser/	
514	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Laser centre	Laser station for welding cutting and additive manufacturing	Celda equipada con una fuente láser de fibra de 2 kW Raycus RFLC2000, con estación, robotizada ABB y distintos cabezales de procesos (corte, soldadura, soldadura híbrida láser-MIG/MAG, cladding).	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/estacion-laser-de-corte-soldadura-y-manufactura-aditiva/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/701	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/estacion-laser-de-corte-soldadura-y-manufactura-aditiva/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; CentroInt: Centro Láser	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/estacion-laser-de-corte-soldadura-y-manufactura-aditiva/
324	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Machines engineering research group	Laser Stereolithography	Esterеоlitografía láser industrial SLA-3000 de 3D Systems	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/esterеоlitografia-laser/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/227	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/esterеоlitografia-laser/	Jose Luis	MUNOZ SANZ	Responsible	Grupo: GI-IM: Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería de Máquinas	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/esterеоlitografia-laser/
515	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Laser centre	Laser-assisted bioprinting lab	El laboratorio de biopresión con láser cuenta con un sistema de impresión mediante Blister Actuated Laser Induced Forward Transfer (BA-LIFT), de tecnología propia, que incorpora un láser en ns Crylas a 355 nm, sistema de visión (incluyendo módulo de fluorescencia) para identificación y selección celular y sistema de posicionamiento automatizado. Permite hacer procesos de impresión mediante BA-LIFT 2D y 3D con precisión micrométrica. El equipo se encuentra instalado en un laboratorio de cultivo celular que incluye campana de seguridad biológica Nuair NUS43600E, centrífuga Thermo Scientific Sorvall ST8 e incubadora Thermo Scientific MIDI 40 entre otro equipamiento menor. El laboratorio dispone también de un microscopio invertido de fluorescencia Zeiss Axio Observer con movimiento en Z y plano X, Y motorizado, sistema de iluminación campo claro y sistema de iluminación de fluorescencia con varios	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biopresion-con-laser/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/703	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biopresion-con-laser/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; CentroInt: Centro Láser	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biopresion-con-laser/
570	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		STRUCTURAL MATERIALS RESEARCH CENTER	LECO OHN836	Analizador del contenido de Oxígeno, Nitrógeno e Hidrógeno en materiales inorgánicos	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/leco-ohn836/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/802	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/leco-ohn836/	Jesus	RUIZ HERVIAS	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; CentroInt: Centro de Investigación en Materiales	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/leco-ohn836/
531	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		hydrodynamics	LIFT and Hybrid Micromachining Lab	Estación de trabajo dedicada a realizar procesos de escritura directa por láser, especialmente por Láser Induced Forward Transfer (LIFT) para procesos de impresión por láser aditivos y de modificación superficial. Permite además combinar procesos aditivos/substrativos con resolución micrométrica. Para ello el sistema combina fuentes láser con diferentes longitudes de onda y duraciones de pulso con sistemas de posicionamiento de haz (óptica fija, escáneres e incluyendo sistema acústico-óptico de focal variable) y muestra (ejes de posicionamiento) y caracterización de proceso (incluyendo sistemas de visión ultrarápidos, viscosímetros, sistema óptico de medida de ángulo de	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-lift-y-microfabricacion-hibrida/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/712	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-lift-y-microfabricacion-hibrida/	Carlos Luis	MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsible	hydrodynamics	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-lift-y-microfabricacion-hibrida/
342	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	Liquid extraction automated system Dionex Autotrace 200	Equipo de extracción de compuestos orgánicos en aguas	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-automatico-de-extraccion-liquida-dionex-autotrace-200/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/643	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-automatico-de-extraccion-liquida-dionex-autotrace-200/	Jose Eugenio	ORTIZ MENEDEZ	Responsible	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-automatico-de-extraccion-liquida-dionex-autotrace-200/
326	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Machines engineering research group	Low cost laser stereolithography	Esterеоlitografía láser Form1+ de Formlabs	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/esterеоlitografia-laser-low-cost/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/233	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/esterеоlitografia-laser-low-cost/	Jose Luis	MUNOZ SANZ	Responsible	Grupo: GI-IM: Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería de Máquinas	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/esterеоlitografia-laser-low-cost/
578	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Luminometer - 2 (Varioskán)	Se trata de un lector de placas de diferentes formatos, que permite realizar medidas de fluorescencia, y luminiscencia y absorbancia de manera rápida.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/luminometro-2-varioskán/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/809	yes	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/luminometro-2-varioskán/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsible	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; CentroInt: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/luminometro-2-varioskán/

INFRA_ID	INFRA_UNIV	INFRA_TYPE	INFRA_DVT	INFRA_RS	INFRA_NAME	INFRA_DESC	WEBSITE_EXI ST	WEBSITE	PHOTO	INFRA_LO AD	SHARE_EXISI TING_RULE	SHARE_LINK	CONTACT_NA ME	CONTACT_LA ST_NAME	CONTACT_PO SITION	CONTACT_RS	AGREE_MAPP NG	AGREE_CATA LOG	INFRA_DOMAINS	INFRA_TEACH RESEAR	SHARE
478	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Magnetic hyperthermia equipment	Este equipo permite realizar experimentos de excitación de nanopartículas magnéticas mediante campos electromagnéticos alternos para producir la generación de calor por parte de estas partículas. El sistema permite trabajar con nanopartículas en muestras e inertes mediante un calorímetro para medir la Tasa de Absorción Específica de energía (Specific Absorption Rate, o SAR), o energía que el campo magnético transmite a las partículas y que induce un aumento de temperatura de cuya medida se puede deducir el SAR. También permite trabajar con muestras a temperatura fijada externamente de manera que el calor producido solo aumenta localmente la temperatura. En este caso se pueden realizar experimentos con cultivos celulares y con animales pequeños (ratones), o con otro tipo de muestras. El equipo puede generar excitaciones con cuatro formas de onda no sinusoidales sino de pendiente constante y controlada desde triangular a casi cuadrada, y una quinta señal sinusoidal en el rango de 100kHz a 1MHz y hasta 10mT de intensidad de pico. El sistema cuenta con una interfaz de usuario que permite visualizar la corriente y campo magnético en tiempo real. El campo electromagnético está generado a través una bobina, dentro de la cual se pueden ubicar distintos portamuestras según la necesidad, que garantizan en todo caso el aislamiento de la muestra respecto del campo generador para la máxima homogeneidad. Balanza de suspensión magnética (Rubotherm MSB Isoorp)	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/magnética/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/652		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/equipo-de-hipertermia-magnetica/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/equipo-de-hipertermia-magnetica/	
343	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	Magnetic Suspension Balance (Rubotherm MSB Isoorp)	Balanza de suspensión magnética (Rubotherm MSB Isoorp)	yes	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/596		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/balanza-de-suspension-magnetica-rubotherm-msb-isoorp/	Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/balanza-de-suspension-magnetica-rubotherm-msb-isoorp/		
527	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials	Makerbot METHOD X-3D Printer - Carbon Fiber Edition Printer	Impresora 3D de filamento para prototipado. Capacidad para uso con distintos materiales poliméricos	yes	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/707		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/impresora-makerbot-method-x-3d-printer-carbon-fiber-edition/	Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/impresora-makerbot-method-x-3d-printer-carbon-fiber-edition/		
471	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Material testing electrochemical device	Equipo universal de ensayos mecánicos de tracción, compresión o flexión con capacidad de carga entre 5 y 1000N. Adaptada para la realización de ensayos in situ en estructuras de interés de interés de controlada. Mediante métodos ópticos de deformación para no afectar a la muestra.	yes	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/651		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/mquina-electromecanica-para-ensayos-de-propiedades-mecanicas/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/mquina-electromecanica-para-ensayos-de-propiedades-mecanicas/		
538	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Laser centre	Mechanical properties characterization lab	El laboratorio de caracterización de propiedades mecánicas cuenta con equipo de desgaste, corrosión, microscopio, medida de tensiones residuales y máquina de ensayos mecánicos. Cuenta además con baño de ultrasonidos, cortadores, pulidora y horno para procesamiento de piezas. Equipo de análisis de corrosión Autolab PGSTAT 128N Se trata de un potenciostato/galvanostato modular de baja corriente, capaz de medir un máximo de 800 mA, con una tensión de 12 V. Tribómetro microtest modelo MT300/NILIN. SMT-A/D100. Se trata de un equipo específico para analizar el desgaste mediante ensayos "pin on disk" and "reciprocating" (normas ASTM-G99 y DIN 50324). Equipo automatizado de determinación de tensiones residuales (sistema hole drilling) SINT Technology. Bastidor de ensayos MTS modelo 318.10 de 100 kN con cilindros elevadores y frenos oleohidráulicos del puente móvil incluyendo actuador integral y célula de carga. Sistema de adquisición y acondicionamiento de datos en ensayos de fatiga. Microscopio Matsuzawa	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-caracterizacion-de-propiedades-mecanicas/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/725		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-caracterizacion-de-propiedades-mecanicas/	Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsable	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-caracterizacion-de-propiedades-mecanicas/	
305	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Model making	Mediterranean botanical garden	El Jardín Botánico Mediterráneo está estructurado en varias comunidades vegetales más o menos características de la zona centro peninsular, como son ericoid carpetano, quejigo basílico, matorral supramediterráneo, alcornocal, coscogor-sabinar y zona riparia. Están representadas muchas de las principales especies características y acompañantes de dichas comunidades vegetales.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/jardin-botanico-mediterraneo/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/330		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/jardin-botanico-mediterraneo/	Juan Pedro MARTIN CLEMENTE	Responsable	Model making	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/jardin-botanico-mediterraneo/	
413	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Control and Automation Engineering	Metabolics	EquipmentUsed For DIGIAC 1750 Transducers & Instrumentation Training Systems (6 Units)Experimental introduction to comprehensive transducer to input and output transducers, signal conditioning circuits and display devices. Used for laboratory sessions of the courses Measurement and Sensors and Electronic Instrumentation. Quanser Helicopter SystemThe helicopter system with 3 degrees of freedom is a simplified helicopter model. In this system, the aim is to design a control system to regulate and follow the elevation and travel angles.Graduation projects and research purposes. Quanser Paper Wrapping SystemThe Paper Wrapping system is the model of the systems used in the industrial paper printing house. In this system, the aim is to design a controller that wraps and unloads the paper at the desired speed and tension. Graduation projects and research purposes. Ball & Beam Experiment SetThe ball-beam system practically corresponds to the problem of controlling the angle of rotation of aircraft. In this system, the aim is to design a cascade control structure to stabilize the ball. An experiment of Control Laboratory course. Fan and plate control systemThe control objective is the angular orientation of a hinged rectangular plate and the control means is by blowing an airstream at the plate with a variable speed. The aim is to design a Control Laboratory course.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/metabolica/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/527		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/metabolica/	Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Control and Automation Engineering	X	X	Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/metabolica/	
523	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials	Metal additive manufacturing printer with SLM Powder bed technology	Impresora de fabricación aditiva metálica Aconity Mini por tecnología cama de polvo SLM. Capacidad para uso con distintas aleaciones de Al, Ti, Ni o Fe (tanto en forma de barras como de polvos). Tamaño de fabricación de 140mm de diámetro y 150mm de altura.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/impresora-de-fabricacion-aditiva-metalica-por-tecnologia-cama-de-polvo-slm/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/693		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/impresora-de-fabricacion-aditiva-metalica-por-tecnologia-cama-de-polvo-slm/	Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)	X	X	Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/impresora-de-fabricacion-aditiva-metalica-por-tecnologia-cama-de-polvo-slm/	
110	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Laser centre	Microscope Renshaw inVia	Microscopio Raman para estudio y caracterización de materiales microestructurados. Proporciona información composicional a nivel molecular Microscopio Raman Renshaw inVia (Financiado con el proyecto C08002C06). Láser ion Ar (514.5 nm). Objetivos: SX, 20X, 50X, 100X. Resolución XY: 1µm	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-raman-renshaw-invia/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/67		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-raman-renshaw-invia/	Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ	Responsable	Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopio-raman-renshaw-invia/	
412	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Microscopy	Servicio de Microscopía del CBGP	yes	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/584		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopia/	Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la	X	X	Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microscopia/		
525	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials	Micro-testing device, SEM microscopy for in situ observation	Máquina de microensayos in-situ para la observación y ensayos dentro de microscopio SEM para distintos materiales.	yes	https://www.upm.es/Portal_in/img/697		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/mquina-de-microensayos-para-observacion-in-situ-en-microscopio-sem/	Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/mquina-de-microensayos-para-observacion-in-situ-en-microscopio-sem/		

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439	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Microtome Leica Histocore NANOCUT R	Microtomo de rotación motorizado.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microtomo-leica-histocore-nanocut-r/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/586		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microtomo-leica-histocore-nanocut-r/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Plátgeno. CentroInt: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la	X	X	Health - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/microtomo-leica-histocore-nanocut-r/
557	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Motion platform 1D	Plataforma diseñada y construida por PICOHIMA para el estudio del comportamiento de sistemas complejos sometidos a movimientos inducidos. Dicha plataforma consta de un motor trifásico controlado por un variador de velocidad FS 122-2411 que, a través de un mecanismo de biela-manivela, genera un movimiento de válvula en una plataforma deslizante. La capacidad de la plataforma es de 5 kg con una superficie de 40 cm x 30 cm. El variador de velocidad permite una regulación de la frecuencia de salida desde 0,1 Hz a 599 Hz. El motor es de la marca Mini Motor, modelo PC 530M4T 20 B3, y tiene	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-movimientos-1d/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/751		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-movimientos-1d/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsable	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-movimientos-1d/
545	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Movement rehabilitation platform	Plataforma de rehabilitación motora de pacientes en domicilio compuesta de entornos virtuales que permiten reproducir Actividades de Vida Diaria (AVD) controladas.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-motora/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/730		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-motora/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-motora/
479	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Nanorobots equipment	Permite la inducción de movimiento a nanopartículas magnéticas para provocar daños en la célula en la que están internalizadas, y así destruirla. Su componente más voluminoso es un imán permanente que permite disponer de una zona de aproximadamente 50x50x20 cm, que tiene una distribución homogénea de campo magnético de intensidad aproximada de 130 mT. Es en ese espacio donde se coloca una bobina de gradiente, fabricada en el laboratorio. Usamos también un equipo de baño térmico de agua para aislar el portamuestras del calor producido en la bobina, de manera que no se alteren	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/equipo-de-nanorobots/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/656		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/equipo-de-nanorobots/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Digitalization - Health Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/equipo-de-nanorobots/
487	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Oral communication lab	Laboratorio de registro y grabación de audio y vídeo con un completo equipamiento que permite la realización de estudios neurofisiológicos de la voz: Cámara panelada sincronizada Estudio de grabación de voz Equipamiento para grabación de alta calidad Videoscopios laringes Electroplografía Electromiografía facial Actigrafía Base de datos de habla patológica y normativa.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-comunicacion-oral/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/644		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-comunicacion-oral/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-comunicacion-oral/
423	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Group of Optics Photonics and Biophysics (GOFB)	Oxygen plasma	Equipo de generación de plasma de oxígeno en alto vacío	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plasma-de-oxigeno/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/542		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plasma-de-oxigeno/	Miguel	HOLGADO BOLAÑOS	Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fotonica y Biofónica (GOFB); CentroInt: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plasma-de-oxigeno/
417	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	P3 Laboratory	Laboratorio de Bioseguridad P3	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-p3/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/530		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-p3/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Plátgeno. CentroInt: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-p3/
456	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Biodiversity and conservation of plant genetic resources	Plant germplasm bank 'César Gómez Campo'	El EGV-UPM es una instalación singular sita en la ETS de Ingeniería Agronómica, Alimentaria y de Biosistemas cuya misión, como miembro de la Red de Colecciones del Programa Nacional de Recursos Fitogenéticos, es contribuir a la conservación de los recursos genéticos españoles y dar servicio, gratuito hasta el día de hoy, a la comunidad científica nacional e internacional y a las empresas que requieren su material bajo lo establecido en los Reales decretos 429/2020 y 124/2017. Creado en 1966, es el banco pionero en el mundo en conservación de especies silvestres. Su colección más reconocida internacionalmente es, sin duda, la de crucíferas silvestres, con casi 500 especies y más de 1.500 muestras, considerada la mayor del mundo. Muchas de esas especies tienen un valor añadido por su parentesco con especies cultivadas del género Brassica. Existe una segunda colección, también muy reconocida, la de especies endémicas de la península ibérica, las Baleares y región macaronésica, en la que se incluye el archipiélago canario. Incluye unas 300 especies endémicas, lo que representa aproximadamente un 25 % de la flora endémica española. Su gestión está actualmente delegada por el Rector en el Dpto. de Biotecnología-Biología Vegetal, en la ETS Ingeniería Agronómica, Alimentaria y de Biosistemas (ETSIAAB). El grupo de investigación implicado: Biodiversidad y Conservación de Recursos	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/banco-de-germoplasma-vegetal-de-la-upm-cesar-gomez-campo/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/587		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/banco-de-germoplasma-vegetal-de-la-upm-cesar-gomez-campo/	Juan Pedro	MARTIN CLEMENTE	Responsable	Grupo: Biodiversidad y conservación de recursos fitogenéticos	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/banco-de-germoplasma-vegetal-de-la-upm-cesar-gomez-campo/
415	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Plant growing lab	Laboratorio de Cultivo de Plantas - Invernadero del CBGP	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivo-de-plantas/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/554		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivo-de-plantas/	Antonio	MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Plátgeno. CentroInt: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la	X	X	Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivo-de-plantas/
64	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)			Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	Plasma generation equipment ICP RIE RONGP901CP	The Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory mainly targets the engineering of an artificial tactile sense in parallel to the investigation of human touch. We develop and integrate novel transducers, both synthetic and bio-hybrid. We implement neuronergic systems, with a neural spiking coding of tactile information. We analyse neural data to unveil the neuronal processes underlying the human sense of touch, and we implement behavioural protocols to characterize the perception of tactile features. This body of neuroscientific knowledge and the developed biobotic technologies converge in a key application domain in upper limb neuroprosthetics, with complementary interests stemming towards safe human-machine co-work, tele-presence for medical robotics and hand-held consumer	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/icp-rie-equipos-generador-de-plasma-prongp901cp/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/511		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/icp-rie-equipos-generador-de-plasma-prongp901cp/	Fernando	CALLE GOMEZ	Responsable	Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	X	X	Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/icp-rie-equipos-generador-de-plasma-prongp901cp/
443	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Bioclimatic architecture in sustainable environment- habitation	Platform for measurement of environmental variables and behaviour in buildings	Plataforma integral de medición de variables termo-higrométricas y consumos eléctricos, compuesta por los siguientes equipos: - 2 dispositivos portátiles de medición y almacenamiento de datos de humedad y temperatura (TESTOSTOR 171-3). - 3 registradores de datos para medición a largo plazo y multicanal de temperatura y humedad (TESTO 177-H1) - 4 dispositivos registradores con doble control de temperatura, con sensor interno y conexión para una sonda de temperatura externa (TESTO 175-72). - 1 registrador de datos de humedad y temperatura de 2 canales con sensores internos (TESTO 175-H2) - 1 dispositivo de medición de humedad, coeficiente de transferencia de calor (valor U), humedad de equilibrio en materiales, y punto de rocío en presión en sistemas de aire comprimido (TESTO 635-1). - 1 cámara termográfica para medición de temperatura sin necesidad de contacto, que detecta la energía infrarroja emitida, transmitida o reflejada por todos los materiales a temperaturas superiores al cero absoluto (0° Kelvin) y convierte el factor de energía en una lectura de temperatura o termograma (FLIR E30 BX). - 1 Gestor Energético Inteligente, que permite verificar en tiempo real el consumo energético total y su coste diario, semanal o mensual del consumo eléctrico, con 3 Enchufes Sensor (equilibrado) (ES) que permiten conocer el consumo individualizado de cualquier aparato eléctrico (ENVI-R de CURRENT COST). - Gateway ENERGODOX para interconexión inalámbrica y gestión de 30 sensores (uz, agua, gas, temperatura y humedad) y comunicación con plataforma online de visualización y almacenamiento de datos recibidos desde Pantalla display Energovision SKU 601175, Transmisor GasSense para mediciones de contadores de gas, y	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-medicion-de-variables-ambientales-y-comportamiento-termo-higrometrico-de-los-edificios/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/723		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-medicion-de-variables-ambientales-y-comportamiento-termo-higrometrico-de-los-edificios/	Fco. Javier	NEILA GONZALEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Arquitectura Bioclimática en un entorno sostenible-ABIO	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/id/infraestructura/plataforma-de-medicion-de-variables-ambientales-y-comportamiento-termo-higrometrico-de-los-edificios/

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534	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Biochemical analysis Group	Sports biomechanics lab	El laboratorio se encuentra ubicado en la planta baja del centro y tiene una superficie de 300 m2. Dispone de 2 Áreas de Registro de Datos y una zona central para el personal; la altura del techo es de 5 metros. La zona 1 de Registro de Datos tiene unas dimensiones de 20 x 5 m con dos fotos para instalación de plataformas de fuerza. La Zona 2 de Registro de Datos tiene 12 x 5 m con un foso para instalación de plataformas de fuerza. Cuenta con un sistema de captura del movimiento 3D marca Vicon con 6 cámaras de alta velocidad. 2 plataformas dinamométricas de tipo piezoelectrico marca Kistler; 1 sistema de electrografía de superficie inalámbrica de 12 canales marca	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biomecanica-deportiva/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/714		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biomecanica-deportiva/	Enrique	NAVARRO CABELLO	Responsible	Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico	X	X	Health - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biomecanica-deportiva/
422	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	Spotter robot BIODOT	The Neuro-Robotic Touch laboratory mainly targets the engineering of an artificial tactile sense in parallel to the investigation of human touch. We develop and integrate novel transducers, both synthetic and bio-hybrid. We implement neuromorphic systems, with natural spiking coding of tactile information. We analyse neural data to unveil the neuronal processes underlying the human sense of touch, and we implement behavioural protocols to characterize the perception of tactile features. This body of neuroscientific knowledge and the developed biorobotic technologies converge in a key application domain in upper limb neuroprosthetics, with complementary interests stemming towards safe human-machine co-work, tele-presence for medical robotics and hand-held consumer	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/robot-spotteador-biodot/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/539		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/robot-spotteador-biodot/	Miguel	HOLGADO BOLANOS	Responsible	Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory	X	X	Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/robot-spotteador-biodot/
464	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Biomedical technology	Stereotactic radiosurgery platform	Equipo que permite la sujeción de ratones para realizar procedimientos quirúrgicos con control de las coordenadas estereotáxicas	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/plataforma-de-cirugia-estereotaxica/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/618		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/plataforma-de-cirugia-estereotaxica/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzadas y Nanomateriales; Centro/In: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/plataforma-de-cirugia-estereotaxica/
537	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Biochemical analysis Group	Surface electromyography by system	Sistema que permite medir la activación muscular mediante sensores superficiales.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-electromiografia-de-superficie/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/721		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-electromiografia-de-superficie/	Enrique	NAVARRO CABELLO	Responsible	Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-electromiografia-de-superficie/
392	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)			Agroecosystem	System for contamination by agricultural practices	Formado por un Analizador CRDS de N2O, CH4, CO2, marca Picarro G2308, basado en un sistema laser con espectroscopia Cavity Ringdown. Incluye además cámaras automáticas de apertura y cierre que permite medir estos flujos día y noche en campo.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-medida-automatica-en-campo-de-flujos-de-n2o-ch4-y-co2/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/521		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-medida-automatica-en-campo-de-flujos-de-n2o-ch4-y-co2/	Antonio	VALLEJO GARCIA	Responsible	Grupo: Contaminación de agroecosistemas por las prácticas agrícolas; Centro/In: Centro de Estudios e Investigación para la Gestión de Riesgos Agrarios y Medioambientales	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-medida-automatica-en-campo-de-flujos-de-n2o-ch4-y-co2/
467	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for biomedical technology	System for high resolution electroencephalography in humans	Sistema de electroencefalografía portátil de alta densidad con electrodos sobre el cuero cabelludo. El equipo presenta 66 electrodos de superficie y 16 canales bipolares para registros intracraniales, con una tasa de muestreo de 5.000 muestras por segundo por cada canal. El sistema incorpora la tecnología de electrodos activos con preamplificadores y mediciones de impedancia tipo LED in situ por cada electrodo, lo que permite reducir significativamente el tiempo de preparación pre-registro.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-electroencefalografia-de-alta-densidad-para-uso-en-humanos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/611		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-electroencefalografia-de-alta-densidad-para-uso-en-humanos/	Gustavo Victor	GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsible	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/In: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/sistema-de-electroencefalografia-de-alta-densidad-para-uso-en-humanos/
554	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Fuel Cells, PEMFC y DMFC) and green hydrogen production via electrolysis	Este laboratorio cuenta con varios montajes experimentales demostrativos para: 1) Equipo que consta de una célula fotovoltaica que al ser iluminada con un foco alimenta un electrolizador tipo PEMFC que produce hidrógeno. Este hidrógeno es posteriormente dirigido a una monocelda de pila de combustible tipo PEMFC que produce una corriente eléctrica que mueve un ventilador. 2) Equipo con funcionamiento semejante al anterior, que se alimenta directamente con electricidad de la red para hacer funcionar el electrolizador tipo PEME. 3) Monocelda de pila de combustible de metanol directo DMFC tipo pasiva.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-doceencia-sobre-pilas-de-combustible-pemfc-y-dmfc-y-produccion-de-hidrogeno-verde-por-electrolisis/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/770		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-doceencia-sobre-pilas-de-combustible-pemfc-y-dmfc-y-produccion-de-hidrogeno-verde-por-electrolisis/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsible	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible; Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-doceencia-sobre-pilas-de-combustible-pemfc-y-dmfc-y-produccion-de-hidrogeno-verde-por-electrolisis/
340	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Environmental studies	Tekmar-Dohman 3100 purge and trap	Purga y trampa Tekmar-Dohman 3100	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/purga-y-trampa-tekmar-3100/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/287		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/purga-y-trampa-tekmar-3100/	Jose Eugenio	ORTIZ MENENDEZ	Responsible	Grupo: Estudios Ambientales	X	X	Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/purga-y-trampa-tekmar-3100/
552	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Test bench for DMFC fuel cell and methanol electrolyzer with climate chamber	Banco de ensayos diseñado y construido por PICOHMA con cámara climática que permite regular la temperatura de trabajo de la DMFC hasta 80 °C. Se compone de un cilindro de O2 y uno de N2 ambos gases comprimidos a 200 bar con una válvula de reducción de presión, controlador de flujo máscico de O2/N2 Bronkhorst EL-FLOW select, humidificador (dos frascos lavadores conectados en serie que contienen agua de grado Milli-Q), controlador de presión Bronkhorst EL-PRESS, depósito de disolución de metanol, bomba Jasco PU-4180, criotermostato de circulación Julabo F33-EH, ventilador 120 mm, fuente de alimentación en corriente continua para el ventilador Ayscom N6700B Ayscom 6 1/2 digit truevolt DMM, multímetro, potenciómetro-galvanostato Autolab PGSTAT128N con módulos FRA32M y BOOSTER10A, ordenador con procesador Intel Core i7 y dos urnas de metanol con intercambiador de	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-y-electrolizador-de-metanol-con-camara-climatica/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/777		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-y-electrolizador-de-metanol-con-camara-climatica/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsible	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible; Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-y-electrolizador-de-metanol-con-camara-climatica/
551	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines	Test bench for DMFC fuel cell with climate chamber	Banco de ensayos diseñado y construido por PICOHMA con cámara climática que permite regular la temperatura de trabajo de la DMFC hasta 80 °C. Se compone de un cilindro de O2 y uno de N2 ambos gases comprimidos a 200 bar con válvula de reducción de presión, controlador de flujo máscico de O2/N2 Bronkhorst EL-FLOW select, humidificador (dos frascos lavadores conectados en serie que contienen agua de grado Milli-Q), controlador de presión Bronkhorst EL-PRESS, depósito de disolución acuosa de metanol, bomba isocrotica para alimentación de combustible, Jasco PU-0196, criotermostato de circulación Julabo F33-ME, ventilador 120 mm, fuente de alimentación en corriente continua para el ventilador Ayscom N6700B, multímetro Ayscom 6 1/2 digit truevolt DMM, carga electrónica Ayscom N330A DC, sistema de adquisición de datos Ayscom DAQ_64-CH o 32-CH, 500 KS/s con acondicionador de señal y adaptador USB, ordenador con procesador Intel	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-con-camara-climatica/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/739		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-con-camara-climatica/	Teresa De Jesus	LEO MENA	Responsible	Grupo: Pilas de Combustible; Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-con-camara-climatica/
563	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Hydraulics for irrigation	Test bench for elements	Consta de una canal donde se colocan las tuberías de riego. Se dispone de bombas sumergidas que elevan el agua desde un depósito de agua enterrados. Cuenta con dos variadores de frecuencia para regular las condiciones de funcionamiento de la bomba. El caudal se mide con un caudalímetro de ultrasonidos portátil y la presión con sensores de presión digitales y manómetros tipo Bourdon.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-elementos-de-riego/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invi/mg/768		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-elementos-de-riego/	Leonor	RODRIGUEZ SINOBAS	Responsible	Grupo: Hidráulica del riego	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursos/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-elementos-de-riego/

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387	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Environment, Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory	Test Tank from the Port Labs in the Higher Technical School of Road, Canals and Ports	El Laboratorio de Puertos y Costas de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid consta de un canal de longitud 52 metros, con sección transversal de 1.00 metro de ancho por 1.50 metros de altura y tiene una capacidad de generación de oleaje regular e irregular de hasta 0.45 m en una profundidad de 1.00 metro. Presenta control de absorción del oleaje reflejado y controla la disipación mediante espuma de poluretano. También se dispone de un tanque o piscina de ensayos tridimensionales, que ocupa la parte central de la nave, tiene una profundidad de 1.30 metros, una anchura de 11 metros y una longitud de 33 m. El fondo del mismo está terminado con pavimento de terrazo „in situ„ y las paredes verticales en loseta continua, dotadas de un sistema de anti-reflexión mediante espumas de poliuretano de 10 ppi. Se genera oleaje multidireccional con control de absorción, con movimiento individual de paletas, pudiendo tener hasta 1.00 m. El aparato generador de oleaje está constituido por 16 paletas de 0.70 metros de frente y 1.30 metros de altura, con las prestaciones siguientes: H = 0.25 m en una lámina de agua de 0.60 m. La informatización del proceso de generación y calibración del oleaje se compone de una estación de trabajo, una tarjeta de comunicaciones, una unidad conversora y una interface con tarjeta de conexión para un mínimo de 8 canales analógicos de entrada en forma diferencial o 16 canales forma común y 2 canales también analógicos de salida. Las instalaciones se complementan con equipos de medida de oleaje, programación y calibrado, adquisición y análisis de datos y...	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/tanque-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invmg/576		yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/tanque-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/	Vicente NEGRO VALDECANTO S	Responsable	Grupo: Environment Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory	X	X	Smart industry and space technologies - Climate energy and mobility	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/tanque-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/	
300	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Environment, Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory	Testing hall of the Port Labs in the Higher Technical School of Road, Canals and Ports	Laboratorio de Puertos	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/nave-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invmg/313	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/nave-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/	Vicente NEGRO VALDECANTO S	Responsable	Grupo: Environment Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory	X	X	Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/nave-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/		
547	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Design and manufacturing engineering	TN-MD-200 de HOYTOM universal testing machine	Máquina electrodráulica de tracción/compresión y flexión con dos zonas de trabajo	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/maquina-de-ensayos-universal-modelo-tn-md-200-de-hoytom/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invmg/756	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/maquina-de-ensayos-universal-modelo-tn-md-200-de-hoytom/	Jose Manuel ARENAS REINA	Responsable	Grupo: Diseño y fabricación Industrial; Centro/Int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)	X	X	Advanced material science and engineering	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/maquina-de-ensayos-universal-modelo-tn-md-200-de-hoytom/		
461	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A scientific or technological infrastructure		Centre for biomedical technology	Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)	Microscopio electrónico de transmisión Jeol 1011 (100 Kv) equipado con una cámara Gatlan-Ortus de 11 Mpx. Incluye los medios necesarios para el procesamiento previo de tejidos biológicos.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-transmission-tem/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invmg/589	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-transmission-tem/	Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO	Responsable	Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/Int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica (CTB)	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-transmission-tem/		
440	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics	Vibratome Leica VT1200 S	Microtomo de cuchilla vibrante	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/vibratomo-leica-vt1200-s/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invmg/603	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/vibratomo-leica-vt1200-s/	Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ	Responsable	Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Plátgeno; Centro/Int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la	X	X	Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/vibratomo-leica-vt1200-s/		
535	Technical University of Madrid (UPM)	A single or several equipment		Biomechanical analysis Group	Vicon 3d human motion analysis system	Sistema que permite calcular los movimientos del cuerpo (velocidades y aceleraciones de los segmentos y ángulos articulares) y del centro de masas en 3D.	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/sistema-vicon-analisis-3d-del-movimiento-humano/	https://www.upm.es/Portal_invmg/716	yes	https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/sistema-vicon-analisis-3d-del-movimiento-humano/	Enrique NAVARRO CABELLO	Responsable	Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomédico	X	X	Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health	Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities	Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosid/infraestructura/sistema-vicon-analisis-3d-del-movimiento-humano/		

Chair of Glass and Ceramics

Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility
Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility

Description

The following equipment can be available in joint research projects within the EELISA network:

Contact: Prof. Dr. Kyle G. Webber

aixACCT TF 2000 ferroelectric testing system (rt-250 °C)

Temperature- and atmosphere-dependent ovens (up to 900 °C) for dielectric measurements and impedance spectroscopy

Impedance spectrometer (Novocontrol Alpha-A Analyzer) and various LCR meters

Screw-type load frames for temperature dependent mechanical and electrical measurements in compression (-150 °C to 450 °C, 30kN)

Aerosol deposition system for room temperature of thick films (ceramics, glasses, and metals)

Contact: Prof. Dr. Dominique de Ligny

Arabica

Raman

Fluorolog

UV-Vis

Furnace to melt glass

Contact: Prof. Dr. habil. Nahum Travitzky

3D printing equipment (powder bed, robo casting)

Contact: PD Dr.-Ing. habil. Tobias Fey

μ CT Skyscan 1172 (max. resolution 0.7 μ m)

3D-FDM printer Prusa mini (PVA, PLA, PETG, ABS, TPU)

3D-stereolithography DLP printer Anycubic (Photon, Mono, Mono X)

3D-stereolithography DWS 020 printer

Injection moulding technology

Contact: PD Dr. rer. nat. Stephan E. Wolf

2x Titrande automated titration systems

Levitation device (4 μ L volume)

Stopped-Flow system (3 syringes, time resolution in the ms regime)

with observation heads (neutron, x-ray)

	<p>with dedicated UV/Vis instrumentation with cryo-quench accessory with automated titration head Dip-coating system Spin-coating system</p> <p>Type: An open teaching laboratory Activities: Research activities Load: Between 50% to 80% used More information available on this website: https://www.glass-ceramics.tf.fau.de/eelisa/</p> <p>Location Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), Department of Materials Sciences and Engineering</p> <p>Contact Dominique DE LIGNY, - Department of Materials Sciences and Engineering</p> <p>Collaboration Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are: - For common research project related to EELISA</p>
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Architectural Conservation Laboratory- Faculty of
Architecture

Culture creativity and inclusive society
Culture creativity and inclusive
society

Description

The laboratory is concentrated on works of characterization of historic building materials, conservation, and consolidation of mortars, plasters, and stone.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Almost fully used

There is no website for this facility.

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Acedemics and graduate students

Contact

Işıl POLAT PEKMEZCI, - Acedemics and graduate students

Collaboration

Architectural Conservation Laboratory/Mimari Koruma Laboratuvarı

Social sciences and humanities - Culture creativity and inclusive society
Social sciences and humanities - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Architectural Conservation Laboratory is a research and teaching laboratory concentrated on the characterization and conservation of traditional building materials. The laboratory is the venue for several graduate courses in the Masters's and Ph.D. programs of Architectural Conservation/Restoration at ITU. The lab provides a research environment for graduate students who are working on these topics.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Almost fully used

There is no website for this facility.

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Sampling/testing/reporting

Contact

Isil POLAT PEKMEZCI, Associate Prof. - Sampling/testing/reporting

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA
- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

computers used for the design and implementation of deep learning algorithms

Artificial intelligenceArtificial intelligence

Description

Monitoring modern technologies and technology development in multimodal signal processing and pattern recognition at ITU.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website: <https://www.mspr.itu.edu.tr>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Artificial Intelligence

Contact

Bilge GÜNSEL, Lab manager - Artificial Intelligence

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)

Earthquake Engineering R&D Lab

Advanced material science and engineering
Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Our laboratory has a small-scale shaking table with test systems that determine some soil mechanics, physical and engineering properties. Triaxial pressure test device with suction control to measure the stress-strain and strength properties of unsaturated soils and the "Hyprop device", which simultaneously determines the water retention and hydraulic conductivity behavior of the soil with the method of drying in open air, have been brought to our university. In addition, the water purification device with a purification degree in the range of 0-1 μ provides deionized pure water to test systems.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Lower than 50% used

More information available on this website:

<https://eedmi.itu.edu.tr/en/research/laboratories/earthquake-engineering-r-d-laboratory>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Geotechnical engineering, earthquake engineering, geomechanics

Contact

Mehmet ULKER, Lab director - Geotechnical engineering, earthquake engineering, geomechanics

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

EMCOL research centre

Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment -
Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences
Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and
mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

EMCOL is designed to combine the trained scientists in Istanbul Technical University (ITU) with advanced field and laboratory facilities for marine and lake studies. EMCOL houses, administers and utilises the upgraded facilities and train new researchers in advanced methodologies in marine geology-geophysics, paleoceanography and limnology.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: www.emcol.itu.edu.tr

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Research Centre

Contact

Kürşad Kadir ERIŞ, Profesör - Research Centre

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

EMCOL research centre

Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment -
Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences
Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and
mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

EMCOL is designed to combine the trained scientists in Istanbul Technical University (ITU) with advanced field and laboratory facilities for marine and lake studies. EMCOL houses, administers and utilises the upgraded facilities and train new researchers in advanced methodologies in marine geology-geophysics, paleoceanography and limnology.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: www.emcol.itu.edu.tr

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Research Centre

Contact

Kürşad Kadir ERIŞ, academician - Research Centre

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

Engine Room Simulator

Artificial intelligence - Digitalization - Advanced material science and engineering
Artificial intelligence - Digitalization - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Ship Engine Room Simulator

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Lower than 50% used

There is no website for this facility.

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Marine Engineering

Contact

Samet BICEN, Research Assistant - Marine Engineering

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

Industrial Design Application Workshop

Connectivity - Culture creativity and inclusive society
Connectivity - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Model making and prototyping workshop especially for the industrial design students. Besides the traditional tools, there are also modern equipment.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Teaching activities, Teaching activities

Load: Almost fully used

There is no website for this facility.

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Model making

Contact

Feyza ERGÜN, - Model making

Collaboration

Innovation and Modeling Laboratory

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility Artificial intelligence -

Description

Innovation and Modeling Laboratory is a laboratory with education and research priority. In the field of architecture, studies are carried out to research, develop and test design, production and evaluation tools. In the laboratory, activities open to undergraduate and graduate students are organized for educational purposes on certain dates.

Students who want to carry out their research in the laboratory should apply to the laboratory supervisor with the Scientific Research Project (BAP) documents with the approval of the coordinators.

The usage area is 150 m²; production, warehouse and working areas are divided into three. The devices in the laboratory are: CNC (1), 3D printer (1), knitting machine (1), ceramic lathe (1), projector (1) and electronic materials

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: <https://mim.itu.edu.tr/ivm-laboratuvari/>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Architecture

Contact

Süheyla Müge HALICI, Laboratory Coordinator - Architecture

Collaboration

Introduction to Electronics Laboratory
Advanced material science and engineering

Description

DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Teaching activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website: <https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Electronics and Communication Engineering Department

Contact

Ibrahim CATALKAYA, - Electronics and Communication Engineering Department

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here: <https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/Labkurallari.pdf>

ITU Smart Grid Lab

Artificial intelligence - Smart industry and space technologies
Artificial intelligence - Smart industry and space technologies

Description

In the ITU Smart Grid Laboratory, we focus on developing ideas and methods using advanced computational intelligence, systems & control theory, and signal processing techniques to facilitate a secure, reliable, and efficient operation of electric power systems in the smart grid environment.

Our research scope includes the secure, optimal operation and control of electric power systems ranging from small-scale low voltage distribution systems, microgrids, to large interconnected high voltage transmission systems.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: <https://smartgrid.itu.edu.tr/>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), ITU Smart Grid Lab

Contact

Istemihan GENC, - ITU Smart Grid Lab

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA
- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

İTÜ-KAT (İstanbul TEchnical University Cavitation Tunnel)

Advanced material science and engineering
Advanced material science and engineering

Description

A large scale cavitation tunnel for hydroacoustic research

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Almost fully used

There is no website for this facility.

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), hydrodynamics

Contact

Ugur Oral UNAL, - hydrodynamics

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

<p>Laboratory of Biomechanics and Strength of Materials Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences</p>	<p>Description</p> <p>Stress Analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Numerical And Theoretical + Experimental <p>Structural Analysis (Dynamics & Static)</p> <p>Structural Testing & Fatigue</p> <p>Material Characterization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Static + Strain-Rate Dependent (Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar) <p>Vibration and Noise Analysis</p> <p>TSI Type Approval - Design Analysis & Testing - of Rolling Stock (& Bogies)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + In close cooperation with numerous Notified Bodies <p>Biomechanics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Modeling and Numerical Analysis + Experimental Stress & Kinematic Analysis + Development of Experimental Methods <p>Fluid- Solid Interaction (FSI) Problems</p> <p>Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure</p> <p>Activities: Research, and others (industrial...) activities</p> <p>Load: Between 50% to 80% used</p> <p>There is no website for this facility.</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Dept. of Mechanical Eng.</p> <p>Contact</p> <p>Emin SUNBULOGLU, Laboratory Correspondent - Dept. of Mechanical Eng.</p> <p>Collaboration</p> <p>Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For common research project related to EELISA - For a predefined cost in the framework of a public funded project
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	<p>- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration</p>
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Measurement, Instrumentation and Control Laboratory
 Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies
 Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies

Description

Equipment Used For
 DIGIAC 1750 Transducers & Instrumentation Training Systems
 (8 Units) Experimental introduction to comprehensive transducer to input and output transducers, signal conditioning circuits and display devices. Used for laboratory sessions of the courses Measurement and Sensors and Electronic Instrumentation.

Quanser Helicopter System The helicopter system with 3 degrees of freedom is a simplified helicopter model. In this system, the aim is to design a control system to regulate and follow the elevation and travel angles. Graduation projects and research purposes.

Quanser Paper Wrapping System The Paper Wrapping system is the model of the systems used in the industrial paper printing house. In this system, the aim is to design a controller that wraps and unloads the paper at the desired speed and tension. Graduation projects and research purposes

Ball & Beam Experiment Set The ball-beam system practically corresponds to the problem of controlling the angle of rotation of aircraft. In this system, the aim is to design a cascade control structure to stabilize the ball. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.

Fan and plate control system The control objective is the angular orientation of a hinged rectangular plate and the control means is by blowing an airstream at the plate with a variable speed fan. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website:

<https://kontrol.itu.edu.tr/en/research/laboratories/measurement-instrumentation-and-process-control-laboratory>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Control and Automation Engineering

	<p>Contact Yaprak YALÇIN, - Control and Automation Engineering</p> <p>Collaboration Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- For common research project related to EELISA- For teaching purposes within EELISA- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)
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MEMS Research Center

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering
 Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

The size of MEMS clean room is 100 m² and its classification is class 1000. The ambient of the cleanroom is controlled so that R.H and temperature are 50% and 20°C, respectively. The service and supporting units cover 150 m², please take a look at both the cell lab and the clean room image galleries below.

The clean-room has the wet/dry etch capability and PVD-based deposition system. There are also several tools for the characterization of microsystems. There are several simulation tools as well; the important ones are Comsol MEMS module and ANSYS programs. Besides, there is a cell laboratory for cell-based studies which is annexed to the MEMS Center. Cell Culture laboratory was founded in 2015 to perform biological applications using microfluidic systems. Cell lines used in mechanobiology and cell separation studies are cultivated in this laboratory in order to carry-out the experiments effectively. We have also access to the ITU Nano Nanotechnology Research Center, If needed, please take a look at www.nano.itu.edu.tr for the equipment available there.

Note: Some equipment may be out of order. Please contact us first to check whether the instrument you need is available or not.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: www.mems.itu.edu.tr

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), MEMS Research Center

Contact

Levent TRABZON, Director - MEMS Research Center

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For a predefined price for any kind of collaboration

Natural Language Processing Lab
Artificial intelligenceArtificial intelligence

Description

Different databases related to languages

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: <https://nlp.itu.edu.tr/>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Turkish Natural Language Processing

Contact

Gülşen ERYIĞIT, Assoc. Prof. Dr., Vice Chair of the AI & Data Engineering Dep,
Director of TURKISH TEACHING APPLICATION AND RESEARCH CENTER - Turkish
Natural Language Processing

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)

Supply voltage schemes, DC characteristics of BJT and MOSFET, transistor amplifiers, linear applications of OPAMPs

Advanced material science and engineering

Description

DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Teaching activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website:

<https://www.elelab.itu.edu.tr/indexenglish.html>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter

Contact

Bora DÖKEN, Lecturer - DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter

Collaboration

Sustainable & Green Plastics Laboratory (SGPL)

Advanced material science and engineering
Advanced material science and engineering

Description

We have devices for Polymer Processing and characterisation:
Twin Screw Extruder GÜLNAR, GM TWIN 16 mm, L/D 30:1
Equipped with cooling bath and pelletizer
Single Screw Extruder ENFORMAK
Equipped with cooling bath and monofilament drawer
Micro-compounder Haake MiniLab
Equipped with co-rotating and counter-rotating twin screws
Internal Melt Mixer Kökbir RTX-M40
Capacity 40 gr
Microcellular Batch Foaming Setup
Equipped with Teledyne ISCO Model
260HP Syringe Pump
Compression Mold MSE-PRESS-SERIES
Rotational Rheometer, Anton Paar MCR 301
Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC), TA Instruments Q1000
Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA), SII 6000 Extar TG/DTA 6300
X-ray diffractometer (XRD), Philips Model PW3710
Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), JEOL 7600F FEG
Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy, Bruker Optics, equipped with
Bruker Platinum ATR

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: <https://sgpl.itu.edu.tr>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), University

Contact

Mohammadreza NOFAR, - University

Textile and Apparel Quality Control and Research Laboratory
Advanced material science and engineeringAdvanced material science
and engineering

Description

Physical and chemical tests and analyzes for textile materials performed in our laboratories are the following:

Physical Test / Analysis for Fiber - Yarn

Physical Testing/Analysis for Fabrics

Chemical Testing/Analysis

Fastness Tests

Washing Tests

Combustion Tests

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website: <https://tekslab.itu.edu.tr/>

Location

Istanbul Technical University (ITU), Textile and Apparel Quality Control and Research Laboratory

Contact

Umut Kivanc SAHIN, Lab Manager - Textile and Apparel Quality Control and Research Laboratory

Collaboration

ISO 17025

Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Artificial intelligence - Health - Smart industry and space technologies
 - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural
 Sciences
 Artificial intelligence - Health - Smart industry and space
 technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - N

Description

The Neuro-Robotic Touch laboratory mainly targets the engineering of an artificial tactile sense in parallel to the investigation of human touch.

We develop and integrate novel transducers, both synthetic and bio-hybrid. We implement neuromorphic systems, with natural spiking coding of tactile information.

We analyse neural data to unveil the neuronal processes underlying the human sense of touch, and we implement behavioural protocols to characterize the perception of tactile features.

This body of neuroscientific knowledge and the developed biorobotic technologies converge in a key application domain in upper limb neuroprosthetics, with complementary interests stemming towards safe human-machine co-work, tele-presence for medical robotics and hand-held consumer electronics.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website: <https://www.santannapisa.it/en/neuro-robotic-touch-laboratory>

Location

Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA), Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Contact

Calogero ODDO, Associate Professor, Head of Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory -
 Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.santannapisa.it/en/institute/biorobotics/visiting-opportunities>

Laboratorio di Storia, Archeologia, Epigrafia, Tradizione dell'Antico

Social sciences and humanities

Description

The SAET Laboratory is duly equipped for managing every step in the documentation of structures, contexts, and items retrieved during field research.

Among the shooting equipment for aerial photography, besides the usual telescopic poles, a UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) is often used to take both digital and infra-red images. Aerial stereophotographic pictures are processed to produce the 3D models necessary to create ortophotos for scientific purposes and other materials for scientific dissemination. A digital microscope allows for the documentation of details from inscriptions, coins and sherds.

Traditional drawing equipment includes a total station and wire pantographs.

The SAET is fitted for producing good resin replicas of inscriptions and other items (the replicas of inscriptions from Segesta exhibited in the Palazzo della Carovana at the Scuola Normale Superiore are a good example).

Cooperation with the SMART Laboratory at the SNS, together with the possibility of 3D printing, open wider perspectives for future work.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching activities

Load: Between 50% to 80% used

More information available on this website: <https://saet.sns.it/it/>

Location

Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS), STG - Polvani

Contact

Alessandro CORRETTI, Responsabile Operativo - STG - Polvani

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA
- For free in the framework of an internship for instance (MSc or PhD level)
- For free if a colleague comes under an Erasmus exchange (training...)

Laboratorio NEST

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

The Laboratorio NEST facilities offer a wide spectrum of tools for your research needs.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website: www.laboratorionest.it

Location

Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS), Laboratorio NEST

Contact

Pasqualantonio PINGUE, Chief Operating Officer - Laboratorio NEST

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here: https://www.laboratorionest.it/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Richiesta_da_ENTE_a_NEST_ENG_rev4.doc

SAET

Digitalization - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

The SAET Laboratory is duly equipped for managing every step in the documentation of structures, contexts, and items retrieved during field research.

Among the shooting equipment for aerial photography, besides the usual telescopic poles, a UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) is often used to take both digital and infra-red images. Aerial stereophotographic pictures are processed to produce the 3D models necessary to create ortophotos for scientific purposes and other materials for scientific dissemination. A digital microscope allows for the documentation of details from inscriptions, coins and sherds.

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Cooperation with the SMART Laboratory at the SNS, together with the possibility of 3D printing, open wider perspectives for future work.

Type: An open teaching laboratory

Activities: Research activities

Load: Almost fully used

More information available on this website: <https://saet.sns.it/it/>

Location

Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS), Classe di Lettere e Filosofia

Contact

Gianfranco ADORNATO, Associate Professor - Classe di Lettere e Filosofia

Collaboration

Possible way(s) of collaboration is/are:

- For common research project related to EELISA
- For teaching purposes within EELISA

3D printer

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Impresora 3D ULTIMAKER 2

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-3d/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Group of Optics Photonics and Biofotonics (GOFB)

Contact

Miguel HOLGADO BOLAÑOS, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biofotónica (GOFB); Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-3d/>

AB200 Laser microprocessing

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Different databases related to languages

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-ab200/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Turkish Natural Language Processing

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Turkish Natural Language Processing

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-ab200/>

Accelerated extraction ASE-200

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Equipo de extracción acelerada (ASE-200)

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-extraccion-acelerada-ase-200/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-extraccion-acelerada-ase-200/>

Activated steam silanization equipment

Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies -
Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy
natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Este equipo usa la técnica AVS (Activated Vapour Silanization, Silanización por vapor activado) para la formación de una lámina delgada de espesor submicrométrico con una alta densidad de grupos funcionales. Dependiendo del precursor organometálico se puede controlar el grupo funcional superficial final.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-silanizacion-por-vapor-activado/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-silanizacion-por-vapor-activado/>

Aerodynamic tunnel S4

Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment -
Climate energy and mobility

Description

Túnel aerodinámico para calibración de anemómetros

Type:

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/tunel-aerodinamico-s4/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Marine Engineering

Contact

Angel Pedro SANZ ANDRES, Responsable - Marine Engineering

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/tunel-aerodinamico-s4/>

AI Image Analysis platform

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies

Description

Plataforma de análisis de imagen por medio de métodos de inteligencia artificial. Cuenta con alta capacidad de computación, almacenamiento y procesamiento de imágenes.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-de-imagen/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-de-imagen/>

AI platform for descriptive and prescriptive analysis of clinical data

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

Plataforma con capacidad de procesamiento y análisis de datos desde un punto de vista estadístico, así como de la aplicación de enfoques de machine learning (aprendizaje automático) a niveles descriptivo y predictivo sobre grandes volúmenes de datos clínicos. Se hace uso de servidores de alto rendimiento para la computación y entrenamiento de modelos en base a la aplicación de algoritmos de inteligencia artificial.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-descriptivo-y-predictivo-de-datos-clinicos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-ia-de-analisis-descriptivo-y-predictivo-de-datos-clinicos/>

Animal lab

Health - Natural Sciences

Description

El animalario del CTB tiene una superficie de 55 m²; la superficie interior útil total es de 30m², distribuidos de la siguiente forma: - Dos zonas independientes para la estabulación de roedores. - Zona de cuarentena. - Vestíbulo. - Pequeño almacén con capacidad de fungibles para una semana de funcionamiento. - Zona experimental de laboratorio para quirófano y estudios de comportamiento. - Zona de instalaciones. La instalación proporciona un ambiente controlado para los animales, con control periódico de dieta, agua, temperatura, aire, ciclo de luz/oscuridad natural, condiciones de vivienda y manejo, además del control de la calidad microbiológica y genética de los animales utilizados en la experimentación rutinaria y exámenes sanitarios periódicos.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/animalario/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/animalario/>

Antenna Testing and Homologation Laboratory (LEHA)

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies

Description

LEHA (Laboratorio de Ensayos y Homologación de Antenas) ha estado trabajando en Mediciones de Antena desde 1980 para actividades industriales, investigación y fines educativos, y está incluido en el Grupo de Radiación (GR) del Departamento de SSR de la UPM. El director de calidad de LEHA es el Prof. Manuel Sierra Castañer y la directora técnica es la Prof. Belén Galocha Iragüen. El personal de LEHA esta formado por el ingeniero Pablo Caballero, el ingeniero Xiaoliang Sun y el técnico Cristian Martínez. Un número variable de estudiantes de tesis de maestría también colabora en LEHA. LEHA se reorganiza con la acreditación ISO 17025 para la medición de antenas. LEHA está incluido en la red: RLA de la iniciativa Madri+d (Comunidad de Madrid).

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/leha-laboratorio-de-ensayos-y-homologacion-de-antenas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Radiation research group

Contact

Manuel SIERRA CASTAÑER, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Radiación; Centro/int: Centro de I+d+i en Procesado de la Información y Telecomunicaciones (IPT)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/leha-laboratorio-de-ensayos-y-homologacion-de-antenas/>

Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) with liquid cell

Social sciences and humanities - Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

El equipo dispone de 8 piezoeléctricos independientes, control Dulcinea®, software WSxM, celda líquida y posicionador XY. Permite realizar toma de imágenes AFM en modo contacto, jumping, litográfico y dinámico (modulación de amplitud y modulación de frecuencia); medidas espectroscópicas de 2 (FZ), 3 (3D-Modes) y 4 (General Spectroscopy Imaging incluyendo Force Volume) dimensiones; medidas de larga distancia con método de doble pasada (retrace) y escaneo de un plano (plane scan). También incluye corrección automática de drift. Además, dispone de un sistema de intercambio de líquido que permite controlar las condiciones físico-químicas del medio en el que se encuentran las muestras. El equipo se encuentra acoplado a un microscopio óptico invertido lo que permite el posicionamiento del elemento sensor en cualquier punto de interés de la muestra.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-de-fuerza-atmica-afm-con-celda-liquida/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-de-fuerza-atmica-afm-con-celda-liquida/>

Biochemicals lab

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

El laboratorio cuenta con un autoanalizador de muestras, fotómetro de llama, lector de placas ELISA, microscopio óptico, congelador (hasta -80°C), centrífuga y contador de células.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioquimica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), ImFINE: Improvement (of health) by fitness, nutrition and exercise

Contact

Maria Marcela GONZALEZ GROSS, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Investigación en nutrición, ejercicio y estilo de vida saludable. ImFINE

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioquimica/>

Bioinformatics Support Unit (BSU)

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

Servicio de Análisis Bioinformáticos

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/unidad-de-soporte-bioinformatico-bsu/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/unidad-de-soporte-bioinformatico-bsu/>

Bioprinter

Social sciences and humanities - Health - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Bioimpresora Inkredible de Cellink

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/bioimpresora/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Machines engineering research group

Contact

Jose Luis MUÑOZ SANZ, Responsable - Grupo: GI-IM: Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería de Máquinas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/bioimpresora/>

Bioscreen

Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Sistema miniaturizado de monitorización de crecimiento microbiano

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/bioscreen/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/bioscreen/>

Cell culture unit

Social sciences and humanities - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Unidad de Cultivos Celulares dotada con equipamiento para la realización de experimentación con diferentes modelos de líneas celulares de origen animal, incluyendo las líneas celulares de origen humano. a Unidad se compone de un laboratorio de nivel de contención biológica 1 (NCB1), un laboratorio de nivel de contención biológica 2 (NCB2) y una zona de lavado y esterilización común. El laboratorio NCB1 está formado por: Una cabina de flujo laminar horizontal TELSTAR 3 incubadores de CO2 Thermo con sensor de infrarrojos y camisa de agua de 80 L y un incubador CO2 Lab-Line para el mantenimiento de cultivos celulares. Un lector de placas por absorbancia Una centrifuga refrigerada Hettich Rotina Un congelador hasta -80°C Una nevera con rango de temperaturas entre -4 y 20°C 2 cabinas de flujo laminar vertical clase II Nuair El laboratorio NCB2 está formado por: Una cabina de flujo laminar clase II Nuair Un incubador CO2 Thermo Scientific 3111 Water Jacket con sensor de infrarrojo y camisa de agua de 80 L Una centrifuga HERMLE Z306 Un microscopio óptico Olympus IX71

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/unidad-de-cultivos-celulares/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Marine Engineering

Contact

Gustavo Víctor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Marine Engineering

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/unidad-de-cultivos-celulares/>

Coating manufacturing

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Equipo de pulverización catódica equipado con dos magnetrones circulares ($\varnothing=5\text{cm}$) y un portamuestras giratorio conectado a diversas líneas de gases (Ar, N y O)

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/fabricacion-de-recubrimientos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Institute of nuclear fusion "Guillermo Velarde"

Contact

Pedro VELARDE MAYOL, Responsable - Grupo: Fusión Nuclear Inercial y Tecnología de fusión; Centro/int: Instituto de Fusión Nuclear Guillermo Velarde

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/fabricacion-de-recubrimientos/>

<p>Cognitive rehabilitation platform Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health</p> <p>Plataforma de Telerehabilitació Cognitiva</p>	<p>Description Guttmann, NeuroPersonalTrainer® (GNPT®) es un dispositivo médico comercial de rehabilitación cognitiva de pacientes en domicilio.</p> <p>Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities Load: More information available on this website: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-cognitiva/</p> <p>Location Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology</p> <p>Contact Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB</p> <p>Collaboration Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-cognitiva/</p>
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Confocal microscopy

Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Microscopia Confocal. Microscopio Leica DCM 3D Sistema para la adquisición de imágenes en 3D de la morfología de la muestra.-Objetivos Confocales: 10X, 20X, 50X, 100X-Objetivos Interferométrico: 50X Mirau

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopia-confocal/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopia-confocal/>

Digital microscope with polarizer

Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Microscopio digital con polarizador Dino-Lite AM4115ZTW con conexión USB, resolución de 1.3 Mega píxeles y tasa de aumento de 10x a 50x.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-digital-con-polarizador/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-digital-con-polarizador/>

DLS measuring equipment

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

El equipo permite medir el tamaño molecular y de partícula de 0.3 a 10 μm , medir el potencial Z de partículas y moléculas a través de Dispersión de Luz Electroforética (ELS) indicando la estabilidad de la muestra y/o la propensión a agregar. Cuenta además con una rueda de filtros ópticos con filtro de fluorescencia para permitir la medida de muestras fluorescentes sin perjudicar la sensibilidad del sistema. Incluye además filtros de polarización (horizontales o verticales) para medidas de tipo DDLS (Depolarized Dynamic Light Scattering).

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-medicion-mediante-dispersion-dinamica-de-luz-dls/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-medicion-mediante-dispersion-dinamica-de-luz-dls/>

Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA)

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences

Description

Absorciometría dual de rayos X (DXA) para realización de densitometrías óseas.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/absorciometria-dual-de-rayos-x-dxa/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laboratory of Exercise Physiology Research Group.

Contact

Ana Belen PEINADO LOZANO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Investigación del Laboratorio de Fisiología del Esfuerzo.

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/absorciometria-dual-de-rayos-x-dxa/>

Dynamometric platforms

Social sciences and humanities - Health

Description

Sistema de medida bilateral de las fuerzas de reacción y del equilibrio de pie que permite medir las fuerzas de reacción en el apoyo y el punto de aplicación de la carga.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataformas-dinamometricas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Biomechanical analysis Group

Contact

Enrique NAVARRO CABELLO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataformas-dinamometricas/>

EBSD detector for crystallographic analysis of metal samples

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Detector Bruker Quantax EBSD 400i con áreas de detección activas desde 10mm² hasta 100mm², Resolución nativa de al menos 640x480 píxeles, preferida de 1600x1200 píxeles.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/detector-ebd-para-analisis-cristalografico-de-muestras-metalicas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials

Contact

Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/detector-ebd-para-analisis-cristalografico-de-muestras-metalicas/>

Equipment for analysis of nucleic acid integrity and quality (Tapestation)

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Equipment DIGIAC 1750 Transducers & Instrumentation Training Systems (8 Units) **Used For** Experimental introduction to comprehensive transducer to input and output transducers, signal conditioning circuits and display devices. Used for laboratory sessions of the courses Measurement and Sensors and Electronic Instrumentation.

Quanser Helicopter System The helicopter system with 3 degrees of freedom is a simplified helicopter model. In this system, the aim is to design a control system to regulate and follow the elevation and travel angles. Graduation projects and research purposes.

Quanser Paper Wrapping System The Paper Wrapping system is the model of the systems used in the industrial paper printing house. In this system, the aim is to design a controller that wraps and unloads the paper at the desired speed and tension. Graduation projects and research purposes

Ball & Beam Experiment Set The ball-beam system practically corresponds to the problem of controlling the angle of rotation of aircraft. In this system, the aim is to design a cascade control structure to stabilize the ball. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.

Fan and plate control system The control objective is the angular orientation of a hinged rectangular plate and the control means is by blowing an airstream at the plate with a variable speed fan. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-para-analisis-de-la-integridad-y-calidad-de-acidos-nucleicos-tapestation/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Control and Automation Engineering

	<p>Contact Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Control and Automation Engineering Collaboration Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-para-analisis-de-la-integridad-y-calidad-de-acidos-nucleicos-tapestation/</p>
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Equipment for dynamic characterisation of viscosity of biological fluids

Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

El sensor ViSQCT es un dispositivo desarrollado en el Laboratorio de Bioinstrumentación y Nanomedicina para medir la viscosidad de un fluido utilizando un volumen reducido (50 μ l aproximadamente). Su funcionamiento se basa en la utilización de Resonadores de Cristal de Cuarzo (QCR por sus siglas en inglés) los cuales son elementos económicos, pequeños y precisos. Los QCR utilizados son con electrodos de oro y con frecuencia de resonancia fundamental de 10 MHz. El dispositivo consta del circuito electrónico, resonadores de cristal de cuarzo, holder del cristal, baterías y software de control.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-caracterizacion-dinamica-de-viscosidad-en-fluidos-biologicos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-caracterizacion-dinamica-de-viscosidad-en-fluidos-biologicos/>

Equipment for extracellular electrophysiology

Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences

Description

Técnica que realiza registros de actividad eléctrica de cultivos celulares con alta resolución temporal y espacial. Servicio de electrofisiología extracelular mediante el sistema de arrays de microelectrodos de Multichannel Systems MEA 2100.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-electrofisiologia-extracelular/>

Equipment for high sensitivity image acquisition (FlumaZone)

Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies -
Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy
natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Microscopio estereoscópico LEICA M205FA de fluorescencia y bioluminiscencia

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipamiento-de-captacion-de-imagenes-de-alta-sensibilidad-flumazone/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares
Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipamiento-de-captacion-de-imagenes-de-alta-sensibilidad-flumazone/>

Equipment for photolithography MA6 with mask projection

Advanced material science and engineering

Description

EQUIPO DE LITOGRAFIA MA6 CON POSIBILIDAD DE ACOPLA DE SISTEMA DE NANOIMPRESION SUSS MA6

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/ma-6-fotolitografia-por-proyeccion-de-mascara/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Group of Optics Photonics and Biofotonics (GOFB)

Contact

Miguel HOLGADO BOLAÑOS, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biofotónica (GOFB); Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/ma-6-fotolitografia-por-proyeccion-de-mascara/>

Equipment for X-ray diffraction for analysis of mineral components Rigaku Miniflex 600

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Equipo de difracción de rayos-X para análisis de componentes minerales

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-difraccion-de-rayos-x-para-analisis-de-componentes-minerales-rigaku-miniflex-600/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-difraccion-de-rayos-x-para-analisis-de-componentes-minerales-rigaku-miniflex-600/>

Exercise physiology Lab (LFE)

Social sciences and humanities - Health

Description

Laboratorio de docencia e investigación en el campo de la Fisiología del Ejercicio que cuenta con distintos equipos como para la medición y evaluación de la condición física, como cicloergómetro, para pruebas de esfuerzo en tapiz rodante, equipo de medición de lactato y analizador portátil de gases.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-fisiologia-del-esfuerzo-lfe/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laboratory of Exercise Physiology Research Group.

Contact

Ana Belen PEINADO LOZANO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Investigación del Laboratorio de Fisiología del Esfuerzo.

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-fisiologia-del-esfuerzo-lfe/>

FDM Fortus 450mc printer for polymeric material and thread material

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

Impresora de material polimérico y compuesto por hilo tecnología FDM. Piezas con calidad industrial. Capacidad para uso con distintos materiales poliméricos ABS-M30, ABS-M30i, ABS-ESD7, ASA, PC-ABS, PC, PC-ISO, Nylon 12, ULTEM 9085, ULTEM 1010, ST130, Nylon12CF, ANTERO 800NA (bajo disponibilidad de filamento). Tamaño de fabricación de 406x355x406mm.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-de-material-polimerico-y-compuesto-por-hilo-tecnologia-fdm-fortus-450mc/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials

Contact

Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-de-material-polimerico-y-compuesto-por-hilo-tecnologia-fdm-fortus-450mc/>

Fiber synthesis equipment through Straining Flow Spinning (SFS)

Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Producción de fibras biocompatibles de altas prestaciones de propiedades controladas. SFS es un método de producción versátil y asequible de fibras regeneradas (producidas con proteínas naturales) y bioinspiradas (producidas con proteínas recombinantes) para producir fibras que combina la biocompatibilidad y el altas prestaciones mecánicas.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-sintesis-de-fibras-por-straining-flow-spinning-sfs/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-sintesis-de-fibras-por-straining-flow-spinning-sfs/>

Filmetrics

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Sistema de medida de espesores e índices de refracción con lámpara halógena

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/filmetrics/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Group of Optics Photonics and Biofotonics (GOFB)

Contact

Miguel HOLGADO BOLAÑOS, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biofotónica (GOFB); Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/filmetrics/>

Fuel cells and alternative fuels lab

Climate energy and mobility

Description

Laboratorio con una superficie de 60 m² equipado con agua corriente, tomas de corriente monofásica de 220 V a 50 Hz y toma de corriente trifásica de 380 V a 50 Hz.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos/>

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (6890/5973)

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Cromatógrafo de gases/espectrómetro de masas (6890/5973)

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-gases-espectrometro-de-masas-6890-5973/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-gases-espectrometro-de-masas-6890-5973/>

Gas mass

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

Different databases related to languages

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/gases-masas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Turkish Natural Language Processing

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Turkish Natural Language Processing

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/gases-masas/>

Goniometer for measuring contact angles

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Goniómetro para medir ángulos de contacto de construcción propia

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/goniometro-para-medir-angulos-de-contacto/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Design and manufacturing engineering

Contact

Jose Manuel ARENAS REINA, Responsable - Grupo: Diseño y fabricación industrial;
Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/goniometro-para-medir-angulos-de-contacto/>

Green Classroom - Educational Greenhouse

Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Invernadero de exhibición, calefactado y con sistema de riego automático. Dispone de un taller de propagación de plantas. En una superficie de 300 m² alberga una colección de más de 200 especies botánicas.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/aula-verde-invernadero-didactico-avi/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Biodiversity and conservation of plant genetic resources

Contact

Juan Pedro MARTIN CLEMENTE, Responsable - Grupo: Biodiversidad y conservación de recursos fitogenéticos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/aula-verde-invernadero-didactico-avi/>

Greenhouses (modeules) of the Centre for Plant Biotechnology and Genomics

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Invernadero (Módulos) del CBGP

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/invernadero-modulos-del-cbgb/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/invernadero-modulos-del-cbgb/>

Heated plates hydraulic press

Climate energy and mobility

Description

Prensa hidráulica MASINOX modelo MGH-30 de platos calientes de 300 mm × 300 mm con capacidad de compresión de hasta 600 kg/cm², regulación de temperatura hasta 250 °C y configuración de ciclo térmico. Refrigeración por agua.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/prensa-hidraulica-de-platos-calientes/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/prensa-hidraulica-de-platos-calientes/>

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC-1100)

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Cromatógrafo de líquidos de altas prestaciones (HPLC-1100) con detector de fluorescencia y diodo-array

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-liquidos-de-altas-prestaciones-hplc-1100/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/cromatografo-de-liquidos-de-altas-prestaciones-hplc-1100/>

Human cell cultures lab

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Laboratorio completo compuesto por 2 cabinas de flujo laminar vertical, un incubador de células, un microscopio invertido y otros equipos auxiliares que permiten cultivar líneas celulares humanas creando las condiciones necesarias para su crecimiento y manipulación segura.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivos-celulares-humanos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Plant Biotechnology

Contact

Isabel Marta ALLONA ALBERICH, Responsable - Grupo: Biotecnología Vegetal;
Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivos-celulares-humanos/>

Hyperspectral camera Headwall E-series SWIR Push-Broom
Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences

Description

Cámara móvil con las siguientes características de número de bandas y espectro:
267 bandas, 900-2500 nm, 640 x N

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-hiperespectral-headwall-e-series-swir-push-broom/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Electronic and microelectronic design group

Contact

Cesar SANZ ALVARO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Diseño Electrónico y Microelectrónico; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías Software y Sistemas Multimedia para Sostenibilidad (CITSEM)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-hiperespectral-headwall-e-series-swir-push-broom/>

Hyperspectral camera Headwall E-series VNIR Push-Broom
Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences

Description

Cámara móvil con las siguientes características de número de bandas y espectro:
369 bandas, 400-1000 nm, 1600 x N

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-hiperespectral-headwall-e-series-vnir-push-broom/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Electronic and microelectronic design group

Contact

Cesar SANZ ALVARO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Diseño Electrónico y Microelectrónico; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías Software y Sistemas Multimedia para Sostenibilidad (CITSEM)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-hiperespectral-headwall-e-series-vnir-push-broom/>

Hyperspectral camera Ximea Snapshot

Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences

Description

El grupo dispone de 4 cámaras móviles con las siguientes características de número de bandas y espectro: 25 bandas, 665-975 nm y 2045 x 1085 (409 x 217).

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-hiperespectral-ximea-snapshot/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Electronic and microelectronic design group

Contact

Cesar SANZ ALVARO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Diseño Electrónico y Microelectrónico; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías Software y Sistemas Multimedia para Sostenibilidad (CITSEM)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-hiperespectral-ximea-snapshot/>

Impact simulation system

Culture creativity and inclusive society - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Sistema para realizar ensayos de choque, evaluar la seguridad pasiva de los vehículos y evaluar el nivel de protección ofrecido a sus pasajeros.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/simulador-de-impactos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Model making

Contact

Jose Maria LOPEZ MARTINEZ, Responsable - Model making

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/simulador-de-impactos/>

Infrastructure for biomarkers and allergen detection and quantification

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

La infraestructura está compuesta por sistemas electroforéticos, lector de microplacas y espectrofotómetros.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-deteccion-y-cuantificacion-de-alergenos-y-biomarcadores/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Plant Biotechnology

Contact

Isabel Marta ALLONA ALBERICH, Responsable - Grupo: Biotecnología Vegetal;
Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-deteccion-y-cuantificacion-de-alergenos-y-biomarcadores/>

Innolas Laser microprocessing

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Sistema preparado para realizar procesos de microprocesado láser usando óptica fija o escaner y pudiendo trabajar en distintas longitudes de onda (IR, VIS, UV).

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-innolas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-microprocesado-laser-innolas/>

Laboratory for fuel cells and alternative fuels with fume cupboard

Climate energy and mobility

Description

Laboratorio con una superficie de 46m² equipado con campana de gases de alto flujo, agua corriente y poyatas de trabajo con tomas de corriente de 220 V a 50 Hz.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos-con-campana-de-gases/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), hydrodynamics

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - hydrodynamics

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-pilas-de-combustible-y-combustibles-alternativos-con-campana-de-gases/>

Laptop 3D printer

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

La impresora 3D de Form 3 del fabricante estadounidense Formlabs, es la evolución de su ya conocida Form 2, elegida entre las mejores impresoras 3D de resina. La impresora 3D tiene una tecnología de impresión: la Low Force Stereolithography (LFS), una tecnología un sistema a medida de láseres y espejos para polimerizar la resina fotosensible. De acuerdo al fabricante, gracias a esta tecnología se puede fabricar 4 veces más rápido y con mayor detalle.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-3d-de-escritorio-modelo-form-3-de-formlabs/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Radiation research group

Contact

Manuel SIERRA CASTAÑER, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Radiación; Centro/int: Centro de I+d+i en Procesado de la Información y Telecomunicaciones (IPT)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-3d-de-escritorio-modelo-form-3-de-formlabs/>

Laser Lumera Super Rapid

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

DC power sources, oscilloscope, multimeter

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laser-lumera-super-rapid/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Electronics and Communication Engineering Department

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Electronics and Communication Engineering Department

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laser-lumera-super-rapid/>

Laser nano and micromanufacturing lab

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

El Laboratorio de Micro y Nanofabricación con láser cuenta con todo el equipamiento necesario para el estudio, parametrización y ejecución de procesos láser con tolerancias dimensionales en el rango micro y submicrométrico en cualquier tipo de material. En la actualidad el Servicio cuenta con fuentes láseres pulsadas en fs con ancho de pulso programable a 1030 nm (EKSPLO Femtolux 30), ps a 355nm, 532 nm y 1064 nm (LUMERA Super Rapid y Spectra Physics Vanguard) así como varias fuentes de ns a 355, 532 y 1064 nm (incluida una fuente de alta potencia en UV, de alta potencia en UV). Todos los láseres están integrados en máquinas o bancadas de proceso y se dispone de escáneres, sistemas de control y conformado de haz y diferentes sistemas de enfoque para poder utilizar cualquier estrategia de irradiación del material y simular condiciones de proceso en entornos productivos. El servicio dispone también de la instrumentación necesaria para la caracterización de los procesos in situ, incluyendo Microscopio SEM Hitachi 3000N, Microscopio Confocal e Interferométrico Leica DCM 3D y Microscopio Raman Renishaw In Via.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-micro-y-nanofabricacion-con-laser/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

	<p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-micro-y-nanofabricacion-con-laser/</p>
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Laser station for welding cutting and additive manufacturing

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Celda equipada con una fuente laser de fibra de 2 kW Raycus RFLC2000, con estación robotizada ABB y distintos cabezales de procesos (corte, soldadura, soldadura híbrida laser-MIG/MAG, cladding).

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/estacion-laser-de-corte-soldadura-y-manufactura-aditiva/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/estacion-laser-de-corte-soldadura-y-manufactura-aditiva/>

Laser Stereolithography

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Estereolitografía láser industrial SLA-3500 de 3D Systems

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/estereolitografia-laser/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Machines engineering research group

Contact

Jose Luis MUÑOZ SANZ, Responsable - Grupo: GI-IM: Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería de Máquinas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/estereolitografia-laser/>

Laser-assisted bioprinting lab

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

El laboratorio de bioimpresión con láser cuenta con un sistema de impresión mediante Blister Actuated Laser Induced Forward Transfer (BA-LIFT), de tecnología propia, que incorpora un láser en ns Crylas a 355 nm, sistema de visión (incluyendo módulo de fluorescencia) para identificación y selección celular y sistema de posicionamiento automatizado. Permite hacer procesos de impresión mediante BA-LIFT 2D y 3D con precisión micrométrica. El equipo se encuentra instalado en un laboratorio de cultivo celular que incluye campana de seguridad biológica Nuair NU543600E, centrífuga Thermo Scientific Sorvall ST8 e incubadora Thermo Scientific MIDI 40 entre otro equipamiento menor. El laboratorio dispone también de un microscopio invertido de fluorescencia Zeiss Axio Observer con movimiento en Z y platina X, Y motorizada, sistema de iluminación campo claro y sistema de iluminación de fluorescencia con varios canales.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioimpresion-con-laser/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-bioimpresion-con-laser/>

LECO OHN836

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Analizador del contenido de Oxígeno, Nitrógeno e Hidrógeno en materiales inorgánicos

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/leco-ohn836/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), STRUCTURAL MATERIALS RESEARCH CENTER

Contact

Jesus RUIZ HERVIAS, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/leco-ohn836/>

LIFT and Hybrid Micromachining Lab

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Estación de trabajo dedicada a realizar procesos de escritura directa por láser, especialmente por Laser Induced Forward Transfer (LIFT) para procesos de impresión por láser aditivos y de modificación superficial. Permite además combinar procesos aditivos/sustractivos con resolución micrométrica. Para ello el sistema combina fuentes láser con diferentes longitudes de onda y duraciones de pulso con sistemas de posicionamiento de haz (óptica fija, escáneres e incluyendo sistema acusto-óptico de focal variable) y muestra (ejes de posicionamiento) y caracterización de proceso (incluyendo sistemas de visión ultrarrápidos, viscosímetros, sistema óptico de medida de ángulo de contacto y tensión superficial, caracterización eléctrica, etc).

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-lift-y-microfabricacion-hibrida/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), hydrodynamics

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - hydrodynamics

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-lift-y-microfabricacion-hibrida/>

Liquid extraction automated system Dionex Autotrace 200
Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

Equipo de extracción de compuestos orgánicos en aguas

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-automatico-de-extraccion-liquida-dionex-autotrace-200/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-automatico-de-extraccion-liquida-dionex-autotrace-200/>

Low cost laser stereolithography

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Estereolitografía láser Form1+ de Formlabs

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/estereolitografia-laser-low-cost/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Machines engineering research group

Contact

Jose Luis MUÑOZ SANZ, Responsable - Grupo: GI-IM: Grupo de Investigación en Ingeniería de Máquinas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/estereolitografia-laser-low-cost/>

Luminometer - 2 (Varioskan)

Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy
natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Se trata de un lector de placas de diferentes formatos, que permite realizar medidas de fluorescencia, y luminiscencia y absorbancia de manera rápida.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/luminometro-2-varioskan/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares
Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/luminometro-2-varioskan/>

Magnetic hyperthermia equipment

Digitalization - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources
agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Este equipo permite realizar experimentos de excitación de nanopartículas magnéticas mediante campos electromagnéticos alternos para producir la generación de calor por parte de estas partículas. El sistema permite trabajar con nanopartículas en muestras en inertes mediante un calorímetro para medir la Tasa de Absorción Específica de energía (Specific Absorption Rate, o SAR), o energía que el campo magnético transmite a las partículas y que induce un aumento de temperatura de cuya medida se puede deducir el SAR. También permite trabajar con muestras a temperatura fijada externamente de manera que el calor producido solo aumenta localmente la temperatura. En este caso se pueden realizar experimentos con cultivos celulares y con animales pequeños (ratones), o con otro tipo de muestras. El equipo puede generar excitaciones con cuatro formas de onda no sinusoidales sino de pendiente constante y controlada desde triangular a casi cuadrada, y una quinta señal sinusoidal en el rango de 100kHz a 1MHz y hasta 10mT de intensidad de pico. El sistema cuenta con una interfaz de usuario que permite visualizar la corriente y campo magnético en tiempo real. El campo electromagnético está generado a través una bobina, dentro de la cual se pueden ubicar distintos portamuestras según la necesidad, que garantizan en todo caso el aislamiento de la muestra respecto del calor generado por la propia bobina.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-hipertermia-magnetica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

	<p>Collaboration</p> <p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-hipertermia-magnetica/</p>
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Magnetic Suspension Balance (Rubotherm MSB Isosorp)
Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Balanza de suspensión magnética (Rubotherm MSB Isosorp)

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/balanza-de-suspension-magnetica-rubotherm-msb-isosorp/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/balanza-de-suspension-magnetica-rubotherm-msb-isosorp/>

Makerbot METHOD X 3D Printer - Carbon Fiber Edition Printer

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

Impresora 3D de filamento para prototipado. Capacidad para uso con distintos materiales poliméricos

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-makerbot-method-x-3d-printer-carbon-fiber-edition/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials

Contact

Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-makerbot-method-x-3d-printer-carbon-fiber-edition/>

Material testing electromechanical device

Social sciences and humanities - Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society - Natural Sciences

Description

Equipo universal de ensayos mecánicos de tracción, compresión o flexión con capacidad de carga entre 5 y 1000N. Adaptada para la realización de ensayos in-vitro en condiciones de inmersión bajo temperatura controlada. Mediante métodos ópticos de deformación para no afectar a la muestra.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/maquina-electromecanica-para-ensayos-de-materiales/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/maquina-electromecanica-para-ensayos-de-materiales/>

Mechanical properties characterization lab

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

El laboratorio de caracterización de propiedades mecánicas cuenta con equipo de desgaste, corrosión, microdurómetro, medida de tensiones residuales y máquina de ensayos mecánicos. Cuenta además con baño de ultrasonidos, cortadoras, pulidora y horno para procesamiento de piezas. Equipo de análisis de corrosión Autolab PGSTAT 128N Se trata de un potenciostato/galvanostato modular de baja corriente, capaz de medir un máximo de 800 mA, con una tensión de 12 V. Tribómetro microtest modelo MT/30/NI/LIN. SMT-A/0100. Se trata de un equipo específico para analizar el desgaste mediante ensayos "pin on disk" and "reciprocating" (normas ASTM-G99 y DIN 50324). Equipo automatizado de determinación de tensiones residuales (sistema hole drilling) SINT Technology. Bastidor de ensayos MTS modelo 318.10 de 100 kN con cilindros elevadores y frenos oleohidráulicos del puente móvil incluyendo actuador integral y célula de carga. Sistema de adquisición y acondicionamiento de datos en ensayos de fatiga. Microdurómetro Matsuzawa Seiki CO. LTD. MXT 30.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-caracterizacion-de-propiedades-mecanicas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

	<p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-caracterizacion-de-propiedades-mecanicas/</p>
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Mediterranean botanical garden

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

El Jardín Botánico Mediterráneo está estructurado en varias comunidades vegetales más o menos características de la zona centro peninsular, como son encinar carpetano, quejigar basófilo, melojar supramediterráneo, alcornocal, coscojar-sabinar y zona riparia. Están representadas muchas de las principales especies características y acompañantes de dichas comunidades vegetales.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/jardin-botanico-mediterraneo/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Model making

Contact

Juan Pedro MARTIN CLEMENTE, Responsable - Model making

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/jardin-botanico-mediterraneo/>

Metabolomics

Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Equipment **Used For**
 DIGIAC 1750 Transducers & Instrumentation Training Systems (8 Units) Experimental introduction to comprehensive transducer to input and output transducers, signal conditioning circuits and display devices. Used for laboratory sessions of the courses Measurement and Sensors and Electronic Instrumentation.

Quanser Helicopter System The helicopter system with 3 degrees of freedom is a simplified helicopter model. In this system, the aim is to design a control system to regulate and follow the elevation and travel angles. Graduation projects and research purposes.

Quanser Paper Wrapping System The Paper Wrapping system is the model of the systems used in the industrial paper printing house. In this system, the aim is to design a controller that wraps and unloads the paper at the desired speed and tension. Graduation projects and research purposes

Ball & Beam Experiment Set The ball-beam system practically corresponds to the problem of controlling the angle of rotation of aircraft. In this system, the aim is to design a cascade control structure to stabilize the ball. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.

Fan and plate control system The control objective is the angular orientation of a hinged rectangular plate and the control means is by blowing an airstream at the plate with a variable speed fan. An experiment of Control Laboratory course.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/metabolomica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Control and Automation Engineering

	<p>Contact Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Control and Automation Engineering Collaboration Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/metabolomica/</p>
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Metal additive manufacturing printer with SLM Powder bed technology

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

Impresora de fabricación aditiva metálica Aconity Mini por tecnología cama de polvo SLM. Capacidad para uso con distintas aleaciones de Al, Ti, Ni o Fe (bajo disponibilidad de polvos). Tamaño de fabricación de 140mm de diámetro y 150mm de altura.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-de-fabricacion-aditiva-metalica-por-tecnologia-cama-de-polvo-slm/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials

Contact

Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/impresora-de-fabricacion-aditiva-metalica-por-tecnologia-cama-de-polvo-slm/>

Microscope Raman Renishaw inVía

Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Microscopio Raman para estudio y caracterización de materiales microestructurados. Proporciona información composicional a nivel molecular. Microscopio Raman Renishaw inVía (Financiado con el proyecto C080020C06)- Láser ion Ar (514.5 nm)- Objetivos: 5X, 20X, 50X, 100X- Resolución XY: 1µm

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-raman-renishaw-invia/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Laser centre

Contact

Carlos Luis MOLPECERES ALVAREZ, Responsable - Grupo: Manufactura Avanzada con Láser; Centro/int: Centro Láser

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-raman-renishaw-invia/>

Microscopy

Health - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Servicio de Microscopía del CBGP

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopia/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopia/>

Micro-testing device, SEM microscopy for in situ observation

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Máquina de microensayos in-situ para la observación y ensayos dentro de microscopio SEM para distintos materiales.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/maquina-de-microensayos-para-observacion-in-situ-en-microscopio-sem/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Advanced structural materials and nanomaterials

Contact

Fco. Javier LLORCA MARTINEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/maquina-de-microensayos-para-observacion-in-situ-en-microscopio-sem/>

Microtome Leica HistoCore NANOCUT R

Health - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Microtomo de rotación motorizado.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microtomo-leica-histocore-nanocut-r/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microtomo-leica-histocore-nanocut-r/>

Motion platform 1D

Climate energy and mobility

Description

Plataforma diseñada y construida por PiCoHiMA para el estudio del comportamiento de sistemas complejos sometidos a movimientos inducidos. Dicha plataforma consta de un motor trifásico controlado por un variador de velocidad RS 122-3411 que, a través de un mecanismo de biela-manivela, genera un movimiento de vaivén en una plataforma deslizante. La capacidad de la plataforma es de 5 kg con una superficie de 40 cm x 30 cm. El variador de velocidad permite una regulación de la frecuencia de salida desde 0.1 Hz a 599 Hz. El motor es de la marca Mini Motor, modelo PC 530M4T 20 B3, y tiene una potencia nominal de 270 W a 140 rpm y un par nominal de 154 N·m.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-movimientos-1d/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-movimientos-1d/>

Movement rehabilitation platform

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

Plataforma de rehabilitación motora de pacientes en domicilio compuesta de entornos virtuales que permiten reproducir Actividades de Vida Diaria (AVD) controladas.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-motora/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-rehabilitacion-motora/>

Nanorobotics equipment

Artificial intelligence - Digitalization - Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Permite la inducción de movimiento a nanopartículas magnéticas para provocar daños en la célula en la que están internalizados, y así destruirla. Su componente más voluminoso es un imán permanente que permite disponer de una zona de aproximadamente 50x50x20 cm., que tiene una distribución homogénea de campo magnético de intensidad aproximada de 130 mT. Es en ese espacio donde se coloca una bobina de gradiente, fabricada en el laboratorio. Usamos también un equipo de baño térmico de agua para aislar el portamuestras del calor producido en la bobina, de manera que no se alteren los resultados por ese motivo.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-nanorrobotica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/equipo-de-nanorrobotica/>

Oral communicatino lab

Social sciences and humanities - Health

Description

Laboratorio de registro y grabación de audio y video con un completo equipamiento que permite la realización de estudios neuromórficos de la voz: Cámara panelada insonorizada Estudio de grabación de voz Equipamiento para grabación de alta calidad Videoendoscopia laríngea Electroglotografía Electromiografía facial Actigrafía Base de datos de habla patológica y normativa.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-comunicacion-oral/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-comunicacion-oral/>

Oxygen plasma

Advanced material science and engineering - Culture creativity and inclusive society

Description

Equipo de generación de plasma de oxígeno en alto vacío

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plasma-de-oxigeno/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Group of Optics Photonics and Biofotonics (GOFB)

Contact

Miguel HOLGADO BOLAÑOS, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biofotónica (GOFB); Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plasma-de-oxigeno/>

P3 Laboratory

Social sciences and humanities - Food bioeconomy natural resources
agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Laboratorio de Bioseguridad P3

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-p3/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares
Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-p3/>

Plant germplasm bank "César Gómez Campo"

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

El BGV-UPM es una instalación singular sita en la ETS de Ingeniería Agronómica, Alimentaria y de Biosistemas cuya misión, como miembro de la Red de Colecciones del Programa Nacional de Recursos Fitogenéticos, es contribuir a la conservación de los recursos genéticos españoles y dar servicio, gratuito hasta el día de hoy, a la comunidad científica nacional e internacional y a las empresas que requieran su material bajo lo establecido en los Reales decretos 429/2020 y 124/2017. Creado en 1966, es el banco pionero en el mundo en conservación de especies silvestres. Su colección más reconocida internacionalmente es, sin duda, la de crucíferas silvestres, con casi 500 especies y más de 1.500 muestras, considerada la mayor del mundo. Muchas de esas especies tienen un valor añadido por su parentesco con especies cultivadas del género Brassica. Existe una segunda colección, también muy reconocida, la de especies endémicas de la península ibérica, islas Baleares y región macaronésica, en la que se incluye el archipiélago canario. Incluye unas 300 especies endémicas, lo que representa aproximadamente un 25 % de la flora endémica española. Su gestión está actualmente delegada por el Rector en el Dpto. de Biotecnología-Biología Vegetal, en la ETS Ingeniería Agronómica, Alimentaria y de Biosistemas (ETSIAAB). El grupo de investigación implicado: Biodiversidad y Conservación de Recursos Fitogenéticos.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-germoplasma-vegetal-de-la-upm-cesar-gomez-campo/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Biodiversity and conservation of plant genetic resources

Contact

	<p>Juan Pedro MARTIN CLEMENTE, Responsable - Grupo: Biodiversidad y conservación de recursos fitogenéticos</p> <p>Collaboration</p> <p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-germoplasma-vegetal-de-la-upm-cesar-gomez-campo/</p>
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Plant growing lab

Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Laboratorio de Cultivo de Plantas - Invernadero del CBGP

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivo-de-plantas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-cultivo-de-plantas/>

Plasma generation equipment ICP RIE RONGP901CP

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences

Description

The Neuro-Robotic Touch laboratory mainly targets the engineering of an artificial tactile sense in parallel to the investigation of human touch.

We develop and integrate novel transducers, both synthetic and bio-hybrid. We implement neuromorphic systems, with natural spiking coding of tactile information.

We analyse neural data to unveil the neuronal processes underlying the human sense of touch, and we implement behavioural protocols to characterize the perception of tactile features.

This body of neuroscientific knowledge and the developed biorobotic technologies converge in a key application domain in upper limb neuroprosthetics, with complementary interests stemming towards safe human-machine co-work, tele-presence for medical robotics and hand-held consumer electronics.

Type:

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/icp-rie-equipo-generador-de-plasma-prongp901cp/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Contact

Fernando CALLE GOMEZ, Responsable - Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/icp-rie-equipo-generador-de-plasma-prongp901cp/>

Platform for measurement of environmental variables and thermo-hygrometric behaviour in buildings

Social sciences and humanities - Health - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Plataforma integral de medición de variables termo-higrométricas y consumos eléctricos, compuesta por los siguientes equipos: · 2 dispositivos portátiles de medición y almacenamiento de datos de humedad y temperatura (TESTOSTOR 171-3). · 3 registradores de datos para medición a largo plazo y multicanal de temperatura y humedad (TESTO 177-H1) · 4 dispositivos registradores con doble control de temperatura, con sensor interno y conexión para una sonda de temperatura externa (TESTO 175-T2) · 1 registrador de datos de humedad y temperatura de 2 canales con sensores internos (TESTO 175-H2) · 1 dispositivo de medición de humedad, coeficiente de transferencia de calor (valor U), humedad de equilibrio en materiales, y punto de rocío en presión en sistemas de aire comprimido (TESTO 635-1). · 1 cámara termográfica para medición de temperatura sin necesidad de contacto, que detecta la energía infrarroja emitida, transmitida o reflejada por todos los materiales a temperaturas superiores al cero absoluto (0° Kelvin) y convierten el factor de energía en una lectura de temperatura o termograma (FLIR E30 BX). · 1 Gestor Energético Inteligente, que permite verificar en tiempo real el consumo energético total y su coste diario, semanal o mensual del consumo eléctrico, con 3 Enchufes Sensor Inalámbrico (ESI) que permiten conocer el consumo individualizado de cualquier aparato eléctrico (ENVI-R de CURRENT COST). · Gateway ENERGOBOX para interconexión inalámbrica y gestión de 30 sensores (luz, agua, gas, temperatura y humedad) y comunicación con plataforma online de visualización y almacenamiento de datos recibidos desde Pantalla display Energovisión SKU 601175, Transmisor GasSense para mediciones de contadores de gas, y Transmisor monofásico 80A + Sensor mini 80A SKU 600815 de consumo eléctrico.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-medicion-de-variables-ambientales-y-comportamiento-termo-higrometrico-de-los-edificios/>

	<p>Location Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Bioclimatic architecture in a sustainable environment-abio</p> <p>Contact Fco. Javier NEILA GONZALEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Arquitectura Bioclimática en un entorno sostenible-ABIO</p> <p>Collaboration Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-medicion-de-variables-ambientales-y-comportamiento-termo-higrometrico-de-los-edificios/</p>
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Platform for monitoring and stimulation of cognitive abilities

Social sciences and humanities - Health

Description

Plataforma tecnológica de monitorización remota y evaluación continua de la capacidad intrínseca de pacientes desde su propio domicilio compuesta por dispositivos y sensores de medida y análisis de habilidades cognitivas, incluyendo un casco EEG.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-monitorizacion-y-estimulacion-de-capacidades-cognitivas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-monitorizacion-y-estimulacion-de-capacidades-cognitivas/>

Platform for monitoring and stimulation of functional activity

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

La plataforma dispone de kits de monitorización de la actividad funcional con distintos sensores y wearables, algunos de ellos de fabricación propia, como un simulador de pérdida funcional, sensores para levantadas, velocidad de la marcha, potencia extremidades inferiores. La infraestructura también dispone de una impresora 3D que permite la fabricación de los sensores.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-monitorizacion-y-estimulacion-de-la-actividad-funcional/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Heat Transfer, Thermodynamics, Turbulence

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Heat Transfer, Thermodynamics, Turbulence

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-monitorizacion-y-estimulacion-de-la-actividad-funcional/>

Platform for surgical simulation and medical training

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

Plataforma de simulación quirúrgica y formación en técnicas médicas dirigida a estudiantes y profesionales sanitarios que está compuesta de: Plataforma de creación de tareas basadas en realidad virtual (no inmersiva e inmersiva), que permite la creación, edición y compartición de tareas formativas de realidad virtual que se adapten a los currículums formativos de los estudiantes. Plataformas de formación y de exámenes clínicos objetivos estructurados: A modo de ejemplo, se permite realizar cursos de primeros auxilios a estudiantes de medicina de forma más inmersiva que los tradicionales. Cuenta con un maniquí físico para la realización de la RCP. También permite interactuar y navegar por distintos órganos para identificar lesiones o poder observar su estructura interna. Simulación de ultrasonidos intracraneal de un bebé prematuro: Permite a los participantes observar el resultado de un análisis por ultrasonidos en el cráneo de un bebé neonato y poder observar los distintos cortes según se navega por el cráneo. Sistema de entrenamiento de manejo de la vía aérea difícil: Entornos web de simulación interactivos que permiten el entrenamiento en tareas de intubación. Plataforma de simulación en cirugía laparoscópica: El equipo permite simular una intervención quirúrgica laparoscópica y gracias al análisis de vídeo detectar en qué fase de la operación está el cirujano. También permite la realimentación sensorial y la creación de vídeos docentes con imágenes procedentes de simulaciones.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-simulacion-quirurgica-y-formacion-en-tecnicas-medicas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Acedemics and graduate students

Contact

	<p>Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Acedemics and graduate students Collaboration Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-simulacion-quirurgica-y-formacion-en-tecnicas-medicas/</p>
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Plenoptic camera Raytrix 3D Light-Field

Digitalization - Health - Natural Sciences

Description

The size of MEMS clean room is 100 m² and its classification is class 1000. The ambient of the cleanroom is controlled so that R.H and temperature are 50% and 20°C, respectively. The service and supporting units cover 150 m², please take a look at both the cell lab and the clean room image galleries below.

The clean-room has the wet/dry etch capability and PVD-based deposition system. There are also several tools for the characterization of microsystems. There are several simulation tools as well; the important ones are Comsol MEMS module and ANSYS programs. Besides, there is a cell laboratory for cell-based studies which is annexed to the MEMS Center. Cell Culture laboratory was founded in 2015 to perform biological applications using microfluidic systems. Cell lines used in mechanobiology and cell separation studies are cultivated in this laboratory in order to carry-out the experiments effectively. We have also access to the ITU Nano Nanotechnology Research Center, If needed, please take a look at www.nano.itu.edu.tr for the equipment available there.

Note: Some equipment may be out of order. Please contact us first to check whether the instrument you need is available or not.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-plenoptica-raytrix-3d-light-field/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), MEMS Research Center

Contact

Cesar SANZ ALVARO, Responsable - MEMS Research Center

Collaboration

	<p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/camara-plenoptica-raytrix-3d-light-field/</p>
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Potentiostat/ galvanostat with current booster and impedance measurement module

Climate energy and mobility

Description

Potenciostato-galvanostato Autolab® PGSTAT128N complementado con los módulos BOOSTER10A y SCAN250.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/potenciostato-galvanostato-con-booster-de-corriente-y-modulo-de-medidas-de-impedancia/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/potenciostato-galvanostato-con-booster-de-corriente-y-modulo-de-medidas-de-impedancia/>

Protein Purification Infrastructure

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment

Description

La infraestructura está compuesta por distintos tipos de cromatógrafos, que permiten separar muestras complejas. Dispone de cromatógrafos de distintas prestaciones (cromatografía líquida de alta resolución, cromatografía de intercambio iónico, cromatografía de exclusión molecular, etc.) que se utilizan de manera acoplada en función del caso de uso abordado.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-purificacion-de-proteinas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Plant Biotechnology

Contact

Isabel Marta ALLONA ALBERICH, Responsable - Grupo: Biotecnología Vegetal;
Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/infraestructura-para-purificacion-de-proteinas/>

Pump test bench

Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Compuesto por un depósito subterráneo de agua para alimentar el bombeo. Cuenta con caudalímetros (electromagnético y de ultrasonidos, limnómetro) para medir el caudal y de manómetros para medir la presión. ir el caudal

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayo-de-bombas/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Hydraulics for irrigation

Contact

Leonor RODRIGUEZ SINOBAS, Responsable - Grupo: Hidráulica del riego

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayo-de-bombas/>

Reciprocating Engines Lab

Climate energy and mobility

GRUPO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

Description

El laboratorio de motores alternativos contiene un banco de ensayos dotado de un motor de ciclo Otto y aspiración natural dotado de los sistemas de control del banco de pruebas y del motor, así como de un sistema de adquisición de datos. Este banco de ensayos permite monitorizar los parámetros de funcionamiento del motor y su respuesta frente al uso de diferentes mezclas de combustibles.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-motores-alternativos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-motores-alternativos/>

Residual stress measurement by x-ray diffraction

Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural SciencesSmart industry and space technologies - Advanced material sci

Description

Laboratorio de Medida de Tensiones Residuales (LMTR)

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/medida-de-tensiones-residuales-por-difraccion-de-rayos-x/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), STRUCTURAL MATERIALS RESEARCH CENTER

Contact

Jesus RUIZ HERVIAS, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/medida-de-tensiones-residuales-por-difraccion-de-rayos-x/>

Scanning electron microscope with focused ion beam (FIB_SEM)

Social sciences and humanities - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences

Description

El equipo FIB-SEM consiste en un microscopio electrónico de barrido (SEM) capaz de tomar imágenes de alta resolución y un haz de iones focalizados (FIB) que puede usarse para eliminar capas sucesivas de la muestra. El modelo es ZEISS Crossbeam 540.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-barrido-con-canon-de-iones-focalizados-fib-sem/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-barrido-con-canon-de-iones-focalizados-fib-sem/>

Spectrophotometer UV/VIS/NIR

Digitalization - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Espectrofotómetro Cary 7000 para la medida de reflexión, absorción y transmisión de luz en materiales y recubrimientos, sobre un amplio espectro de radiación electromagnética, desde el ultravioleta al infrarrojo cercano pasando por el visible

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/espectrofotometro-uv-vis-nir/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Institute of Solar Energy

Contact

Carlos Del CAÑIZO NADAL, Responsable - Grupo: Silicio y Nuevos Conceptos para Células Solares; Centro/int: Instituto de Energía Solar

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/espectrofotometro-uv-vis-nir/>

Spinner

Health - Smart industry and space technologies - Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Equipo para depósitos de láminas delgadas

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/spinner/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Group of Optics Photonics and Biofotonics (GOFB)

Contact

Miguel HOLGADO BOLAÑOS, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Óptica Fónica y Biofotónica (GOFB); Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/spinner/>

Sports biomechanics lab

Health - Natural Sciences

Description

El laboratorio se encuentra ubicado en la planta baja del centro y tiene una superficie de 300 m². Dispone de 2 áreas de Registro de Datos y una zona central para el personal; la altura del techo es de 5 metros. La zona 1 de Registro de Datos tiene unas dimensiones de 20 x 5 m con dos fosos para instalación de plataformas de fuerza. La Zona 2 de Registro de Datos tiene 12 x 5 m con un foso para instalación de plataformas de fuerza. Cuenta con un sistema de captura del movimiento 3D marca Vicon con 6 cámaras de alta velocidad, 2 plataformas dinamométricas de tipo piezoeléctrico marca Kistler, 1 sistema de electromiografía de superficie inalámbrica de 12 canales marca Delsys.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biomecanica-deportiva/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Biomechanical analysis Group

Contact

Enrique NAVARRO CABELLO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-biomecanica-deportiva/>

Spotter robot BIODOT

Artificial intelligence - Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

The Neuro-Robotic Touch laboratory mainly targets the engineering of an artificial tactile sense in parallel to the investigation of human touch.

We develop and integrate novel transducers, both synthetic and bio-hybrid. We implement neuromorphic systems, with natural spiking coding of tactile information.

We analyse neural data to unveil the neuronal processes underlying the human sense of touch, and we implement behavioural protocols to characterize the perception of tactile features.

This body of neuroscientific knowledge and the developed biorobotic technologies converge in a key application domain in upper limb neuroprosthetics, with complementary interests stemming towards safe human-machine co-work, tele-presence for medical robotics and hand-held consumer electronics.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/robot-spotteador-biodot/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Contact

Miguel HOLGADO BOLAÑOS, Responsable - Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/robot-spotteador-biodot/>

Stereotactic radiosurgery platform

Social sciences and humanities - Health

Description

Equipo que permite la sujeción de ratones para realizar procedimientos quirúrgicos con control de las coordenadas estereotáxicas

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-cirugia-estereotaxica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/plataforma-de-cirugia-estereotaxica/>

Surface electromyography system

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

Sistema que permite medir la activación muscular mediante sensores superficiales.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-electromiografia-de-superficie/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Biomechanical analysis Group

Contact

Enrique NAVARRO CABELLO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-electromiografia-de-superficie/>

System for automated measurement in N₂O, CH₄ and CO₂ flows

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Food bioeconomy
natural resources agriculture and environment - Natural Sciences

Description

Formado por un Analizador CRDS de N₂O, CH₄, CO₂, marca Picarro G2308, basado en un sistema laser con espectroscopia Cavity Ringdown. Incluye además cámaras automáticas de apertura y cierre que permite medir estos flujos día y noche en campo.

Type:

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-medida-automatica-en-campo-de-flujos-de-n2o-ch4-y-co2/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Agroecosystems contamination by agricultural practices

Contact

Antonio VALLEJO GARCIA, Responsable - Grupo: Contaminación de agroecosistemas por las prácticas agrícolas; Centro/int: Centro de Estudios e Investigación para la Gestión de Riesgos Agrarios y Medioambientales (CEIGRAM)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-medida-automatica-en-campo-de-flujos-de-n2o-ch4-y-co2/>

System for high density electroencephalography in humans

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

Sistema de electroencefalografía portátil de alta densidad con electrodos activos para uso en personas. El equipo presenta 96 electrodos de superficie y 16 canales bipolares para registros intracraneales, con una tasa de muestreo de 5.000 muestras por segundo por cada canal. El sistema incorpora la tecnología de electrodos activos con preamplificadores y mediciones de impedancia tipo LED in situ por cada electrodo, lo que permite reducir significativamente el tiempo de preparación pre-registro.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-electroencefalografia-de-alta-densidad-para-uso-en-humanos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-de-electroencefalografia-de-alta-densidad-para-uso-en-humanos/>

Teaching lab on fuel cells (PEMFC y DMFC) and green hydrogen production via electrolysis

Health

Description

Este laboratorio cuenta con varios montajes experimentales demostrativos para docencia: 1) Equipo que consta de una célula fotovoltaica que al ser iluminada con un foco alimenta un electrolizador tipo PEME que produce hidrógeno. Este hidrógeno es posteriormente dirigido a una monocelda de pila de combustible tipo PEMFC que produce una corriente eléctrica que mueve un ventilador. 2) Equipo con funcionamiento semejante al anterior, que se alimenta directamente con electricidad de la red para hacer funcionar el electrolizador tipo PEME. 3) Monocelda de pila de combustible de metanol directo DMFC tipo pasiva.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-docencia-sobre-pilas-de-combustible-pemfc-y-dmfc-y-produccion-de-hidrogeno-verde-por-electrolisis/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/laboratorio-de-docencia-sobre-pilas-de-combustible-pemfc-y-dmfc-y-produccion-de-hidrogeno-verde-por-electrolisis/>

Tekmar-Dohrman 3100 purge and trap

Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment -
Climate energy and mobility

Description

Purga y trampa Tekmar-Dohrman 3100

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/purga-y-trampa-tekmar-dohrman-3100/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environmental studies

Contact

Jose Eugenio ORTIZ MENENDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Estudios Ambientales

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/purga-y-trampa-tekmar-dohrman-3100/>

Test bench for DMFC fuel cell and methanol electrolyzer with climate chamber

Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Banco de ensayos diseñado y construido por PiCoHiMA con cámara climática que permite regular la temperatura de trabajo de la DMFC o el electrolizador de metanol hasta 80 °C y ensayar estos dispositivos con tensión e intensidad de corriente máximas de 10 V y 10 A, respectivamente. Se compone de un cilindro de O₂ y uno de N₂ ambos gases comprimidos a 200 bar con una válvula de reducción de presión, controlador de flujo másico de O₂/N₂ Bronkhorst EL-FLOW select, humidificador (dos frascos lavadores conectados en serie que contienen agua de grado Milli-Q), controlador de presión Bronkhorst EL-PRESS, depósito de disolución de metanol, bomba Jasco PU-4180, criotermostato de circulación Julabo F33-EH, ventilador 120 mm, fuente de alimentación en corriente continua para el ventilador Ayscom N6700B Ayscom 6 1/2 digit truevolt DMM, multímetro, potencióstato-galvanostato Autolab PGSTAT128N con módulos FRA32M y BOOSTER10A, ordenador con procesador Intel Core i7 y dos urnas de metacrilato con intercambiador de calor.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-y-electrolizador-de-metanol-con-camara-climatica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

	<p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-y-electrolizador-de-metanol-con-camara-climatica/</p>
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Test bench for DMFC fuel cell with climate chamber

Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility

Description

Banco de ensayos diseñado y construido por PiCoHiMA con cámara climática que permite regular la temperatura de trabajo de la DMFC hasta 80 °C. Se compone de un cilindro de O₂ y uno de N₂ ambos gases comprimidos a 200 bar con válvula de reducción de presión, controlador de flujo másico de O₂/N₂ Bronkhorst EL-FLOW select, humidificador (dos frascos lavadores conectados en serie que contienen agua de grado Milli-Q), controlador de presión Bronkhorst EL-PRESS, depósito de disolución acuosa de metanol, bomba isocrática para alimentación de combustible Jasco PU-2086, criotermostato de circulación Julabo F33-ME, ventilador 120 mm, fuente de alimentación en corriente continua para el ventilador Ayscom N6700B, multímetro Ayscom 6 1/2 digit truevolt DMM, carga electrónica Ayscom N3304A DC, sistema de adquisición de datos Ayscom DAQ, 64-CH or 32-CH; 500 KS/s con acondicionador de señal y adaptador USB, ordenador con procesador Intel Core i7 y dos urnas de metacrilato con intercambiador de calor.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-con-camara-climatica/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Fuel Cells, Hydrogen Technology and Alternative Engines

Contact

Teresa De Jesus LEO MENA, Responsable - Grupo: Pilas de Combustible, Tecnología del Hidrógeno y Motores Alternativos

Collaboration

	<p>Sharing rules are available here: https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-pila-de-combustible-dmfc-con-camara-climatica/</p>
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Test bench for irrigation elements

Smart industry and space technologies - Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment - Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Consta de una canal donde se colocan las tuberías de riego. Se dispone de dos bombas sumergidas que elevan el agua desde dos depósitos de agua enterrados. Cuenta con dos variadores de frecuencia para regular las condiciones de funcionamiento de la bomba. El caudal se mide con un caudalímetro de ultrasonidos portátil y la presión con sensores de presión digitales y manómetros tipo Bourdon.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-elementos-de-riego/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Hydraulics for irrigation

Contact

Leonor RODRIGUEZ SINOBAS, Responsable - Grupo: Hidráulica del riego

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/banco-de-ensayos-de-elementos-de-riego/>

Test Tank from the Port Labs in the Higher Technical School of Road, Canals and Ports

Smart industry and space technologies - Climate energy and mobility

Description

El Laboratorio de Puertos y Costas de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid consta de un canal de longitud 52 metros, con sección transversal de 1.00 metro de ancho por 1.50 metros de altura y tiene una capacidad de generación de oleaje regular e irregular de hasta 0.45 m en una profundidad de 1.00 metro. Presenta control de absorción del oleaje reflejado y controla la disipación mediante espuma de poliuretano. También se dispone de un tanque o piscina de ensayos tridimensionales, que ocupa la parte central de la nave, tiene una profundidad de 1.36 metros, una anchura de 11 metros y una longitud de 33 m. El fondo del mismo está terminado con pavimento de terrazo ζ in situ ζ y las paredes verticales en loseta continua, dotadas de un sistema de anti reflexión mediante espumas de poliuretano de 10 ppi. Se genera oleaje multidireccional con control de absorción, con movimiento individual de palas, pudiendo llenar hasta 1.00 m. El aparato generador de oleaje está constituido por 16 paletas de 0.70 metros de frente y 1.30 metros de altura, con las prestaciones siguientes: $H = 0.25$ m en una lámina de agua de 0.60 m. La informatización del proceso de generación y calibración del oleaje se compone de una estación de trabajo, una tarjeta de comunicaciones, una unidad conversora y una interface con tarjeta de conexión para un mínimo de 8 canales analógicos de entrada en forma diferencial o 16 canales forma común y 2 canales también analógicos de salida. Las instalaciones se complementan con equipos de medida de oleaje, programación y calibrado, adquisición y análisis de datos y un pequeño centro de cálculo con modelos matemáticos y numéricos de contraste.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/tanque-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-de-la-escuela-tecnica-superior-de-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/>

Location

	<p>Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environment, Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory</p> <p>Contact</p> <p>Vicente NEGRO VALDECANTOS, Responsable - Grupo: Environment Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory</p> <p>Collaboration</p> <p>Sharing rules are available here:</p> <p>https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/tanque-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-de-la-escuela-tecnica-superior-de-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/</p>
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Testing hall of the Port Labs in the Higher Technical School of Road, Canals and Ports
Climate energy and mobility - Natural Sciences

Description

Laboratorio de Puertos

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/nave-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Environment, Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory

Contact

Vicente NEGRO VALDECANTOS, Responsable - Grupo: Environment Coast and Ocean Research Laboratory

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/nave-de-ensayos-del-laboratorio-de-puertos-ets-ingenieros-de-caminos-canales-y-puertos/>

TN-MD-200 de HOYTOM universal testing machine
Advanced material science and engineering

Description

Máquina electrohidráulica de tracción/compresión y flexión con dos zonas de trabajo

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/maquina-de-ensayos-universal-modelo-tn-md-200-de-hoytom/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Design and manufacturing engineering

Contact

Jose Manuel ARENAS REINA, Responsable - Grupo: Diseño y fabricación industrial;
Centro/int: Centro de Investigación en Materiales Estructurales (CIME)

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/maquina-de-ensayos-universal-modelo-tn-md-200-de-hoytom/>

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Social sciences and humanities - Advanced material science and engineering - Natural Sciences

Description

Microscopio electrónico de transmisión Jeol 1011 (100 Kv) equipado con una cámara Gatan-Orius de 11 Mpx. Incluye los medios necesarios para el procesamiento previo de tejidos biológicos.

Type: A scientific or technological infrastructure

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-transmision-tem/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for biomedical technology

Contact

Gustavo Victor GUINEA TORTUERO, Responsable - Grupo: Materiales Estructurales Avanzados y Nanomateriales; Centro/int: Centro de Tecnología Biomédica CTB

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/microscopio-electronico-de-transmision-tem/>

Vibratome Leica VT1200 S

Food bioeconomy natural resources agriculture and environment -
Natural Sciences

Description

Microtomo de cuchilla vibrante

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/vibratomo-leica-vt1200-s/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Centre for plant biotechnology and genomics

Contact

Antonio MOLINA FERNANDEZ, Responsable - Grupo: Interacciones Moleculares
Planta-Patógeno; Centro/int: Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de la plantas

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/vibratomo-leica-vt1200-s/>

Vicon 3d human motion analysis system

Social sciences and humanities - Digitalization - Health

Description

Sistema que permite calcular los movimientos del cuerpo (velocidades y aceleraciones de los segmentos y ángulos articulares) y del centro de masas en 3D.

Type: A single or several equipment

Activities: Research, Teaching, and others (industrial...) activities

Load:

More information available on this website:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-vicon-analisis-3d-del-movimiento-humano/>

Location

Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Biomechanical analysis Group

Contact

Enrique NAVARRO CABELLO, Responsable - Grupo: Grupo de Análisis Biomecánico

Collaboration

Sharing rules are available here:

<https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/infraestructura/sistema-vicon-analisis-3d-del-movimiento-humano/>